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SENSORY ANALYSIS AS A TOOL TO IMPROVE THE QUALITY OF
AQUACULTURE PRODUCTS

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ABSTRACT

Sensory analysis is a scientific discipline used to evoke, measure, analyse and interpret the responses to products that are perceived by the senses of sight, smell, taste, touch and hearing.

This science is used to highlight the strengths and characteristics of a product, such as in the case of research and development products where alternative ingredients, food waste or by-products are used. It can also be used to evaluate the same characteristics over time, to highlight alterations in one of the sensory components at a given time or over time.

This doctoral thesis deals with the valorisation, through characterisation, of various aquaculture fish products. In particular, the products covered by this study were analysed, depending on the objective pursued, with different sensory methods using trained judges and in one case consumers.

Therefore, the sensory characterisation of the products was useful for investigating the foods considered in this doctoral research.

In particular, specific research topics were taken:

1. The study of alternative ingredients, such as the outcomes of different levels of inclusion of insect larvae (*Hermetia illucens*) meal on the quality of sea bream (*Sparus aurata*) fillets.
2. The study of consumer expectations and perceptions on the use of insect meal as a feed for aquaculture products. In particular, this study was done after the characterisation by Quantitative Descriptive analysis (QDA[®]) of the products to exclude sensory differences.
3. Development of a non-destructive and cheap device based on dielectric spectroscopy for assessing fish freshness. In particular in this study, the developed device was evaluated in correlation with a sensory method for assessing the freshness of fish product, the Quality Index Method (QIM)

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1. QUALITY OF FOOD PRODUCTS

1.1 The evolution of the concept of quality

The origin of the term quality is very ancient. The first evidence of the concept of quality is found in Hammurabi's Code of the 18th century BC. It was the Phoenicians around 1200 B.C. who established the first group of inspectors with extensive powers whose task was to control the quality of the workers' work. From a modern perspective, the concept of quality began to develop in the early Middle Ages. In fact, the Middle Ages witnessed major innovations that gave great impetus to the development of the concept of quality. This period saw the birth of the Guilds of Arts and Crafts. These were bodies set up to protect categories of workers and their activities, and in fact established the figure of the 'master' to guarantee the reproducibility of deliveries, which is a fundamental aspect of quality. During this period, another element reminiscent of modern models of high quality was created: the application of the mark. If the customer ascertains by signature or stamp that the delivered product has been produced in-house, he guarantees its quality at his own risk. In this historical period, the concept of quality falls within the scope of craftsmanship (Pulvirenti and De Giorgio, 2017)

The further development of the concept and quality control then moved to England during the First Industrial Revolution. Thanks to the thermal energy obtained from coal, the transport of goods by rail and the advent of the first machines, small-scale craftwork was replaced by numerous industrial enterprises. Never before has the formalisation of product research and production projects been the basis for the achievement of quality goals.

One of the factors linking the First and Second Industrial Revolution was the optimisation of blue-collar labour, which reached its peak with Henry Ford's assembly line, then later with the advent of electricity and early technology (Pulvirenti and De Giorgio, 2017). In the 1920s, the demand for products increased, costs decreased, and activities were handled in large quantities and repeatedly by unskilled workers. The Ford model maximised the work of its workers. However, the greater the number, the greater the likelihood of errors occurring. Thus, a first statistical model was created based on the control card with the aim of verifying the quality of the product after the final inspection.

Control Charts, therefore, use statistics to assess the quality of an entire batch of a given finished product and were first applied during the Second World War, precisely in the war industry, which had to ensure supplies in large quantities at low costs. well-trained worker. female employees, so the possibility of errors is very high. By the end of World War II, quality control ensured better processes and products at lower costs. In the post-war period, quality control techniques were introduced in

Japan by Deming and Juran, leading to the development and success of Japanese industry (Pulvirenti and De Giorgio, 2017).

The Japanese state has made a significant contribution to the development of the quality industry: it was here that the Union of Japanese Scientists and Engineers (JUSE) was founded, which continues to promote the development and dissemination of quality control to a much greater extent. In 1949, they founded the Quality Control Research Group (QCRG). However, there is still a missing piece in the large mosaic of quality; it is still a concept that only encompasses the company or craft producer, but quality is determined by all production processes: from the sourcing of raw materials to the external services used or subcontracted, to the training of employees, etc... .

In 1951, Feigenbaum published TQC - Total Quality Control (Tsfay, 2021), a book proposing a consumer-oriented corporate attitude, with clear quality objectives based on these needs and with the attitude involving the entire structure through motivating employees to pursue the goal of continuous improvement. "Total quality control is an effective system for integrating the quality development, quality maintenance, and quality improvement efforts of the various groups in an organization so as to enable production and service at the most economical levels which allow full customer satisfaction" (Feigenbaum, 1983).

The emphasis on quality is evolving towards customer centricity, focusing on the satisfaction of customers who will use the goods or services they purchase. Eight years later, the first quality standard was published: MIL-Q-9858A - Quality Programme Requirements - a military quality assurance standard. This standard was used by NATO in a series of standards that would form the basis for the revision of quality systems for the first time.

The last decade of the 1900s represented the economic boom, globalisation, internationalisation, the growth of supply to the point of outstripping demand. Everything became faster: products and services innovated and then quickly replaced each other. It was during this decade that consumers became the judges of quality. In order to be able to satisfy customers, it is necessary to use the Total Quality approach introduced in Japan as Company-Wide Quality Control (CWQC) - a way to provide good products at a low cost by distributing the benefits among consumers, employees and shareholders to improve quality of human life (Pala, 1994) - and in the United States as Total Quality Control (TQC) - a system that integrates quality technology into all business functions to achieve customer satisfaction (Pala, 1994). The Total Quality approach requires that the company, at all levels, responds through continuous development to all customer needs and thus achieves Quality objectives.

Giving a definition of 'quality' is not easy. This concept is constantly evolving, depending on context and needs. An interesting aspect of this concept is its permeability over time and between fields;

indeed, this is always the goal to be achieved in any field: quality of life, quality of raw materials, quality of service, etc.

Here are two definitions:

"Quality: is the set of properties and characteristics that give a product, a manufacturing process or a service the capacity to satisfy expressed or implied requirements (SO 8402:1995)".

"Quality: is the degree to which a set of intrinsic characteristics satisfies requirements. The term quality does not express a level of merit in a comparative sense. Quality takes on two fundamental aspects: that of conformity to standards and that of quality management, understood as the overall strategic management philosophy of the company. (ISO 9000:2015)".

In this regard, it is useful to elaborate on Professor Noriaki Kano's model introduced in the early 1980s, which explains the consumer's perception of quality through the satisfaction of his needs or requirements, articulated as follows (Murmura, 2012):

- Implicit requirements or must be (generate implicit quality)

These are the basic needs of the consumer, those linked to previous experience, and which are taken for granted. The existence of these factors does not, in fact, generate any positive impact on consumer satisfaction; on the contrary, the absence of these factors makes the good or service non-compliant, leading to its failure on the market.

- Performance or one-dimensional requirements (generate implicit quality)

These are the needs declared by the consumer and which will be used by him to generate a comparison with competing goods or services. From these needs, the direct proportionality between the product's performance need and customer satisfaction can be deduced.

- Latent or attractive requirements (generate latent quality)

These are the needs that the consumer is completely unaware of having and which, once satisfied, generate an exponential increase in customer satisfaction and therefore in the perception of product quality.

Figure 1. The Kano model of customer satisfaction (Kano et al., 1984).

In conclusion, giving a definition of quality is not easy, considering the speed of evolution of the concept and the subjective component implicit in it. We can therefore say that quality is the meeting point between different needs: the company must satisfy the needs and demands of consumers, that is their needs.

1.2 Sensory quality

All food products are made up of molecules, such as proteins, lipids, phospholipids, etc. They play a physiological role in sensory perception. All these molecules produce effects that we could call 'sensory qualities' on our five sense organs (smell, taste, touch, sight and hearing). Consumers prioritise sensory quality because no perfect packaging, commitment to sustainability or marketing strategy can compensate for unacceptable sensory quality. Therefore, it is important that companies evaluate the sensory quality of products through sensory analysis and understand that the products that satisfy consumers are those with sensory characteristics like the customer's taste.

2. SENSORY ANALYSIS

The history of sensory analysis is relatively young, but its origins are ancient. The quality of a product has always been controlled at the sensory level. From the very beginning, the human senses have been the first check on food, both to assess its quality and to evaluate its safety.

Sensory analysis officially took shape in the 1940s, when researchers at the Quartermaster Food and Container Institute for the Armed Forces, the military department responsible for catering in the US Army, realised that a proportion of soldiers found the food they were given to be palatable while another proportion did not. Having established that the factor that most influences the enjoyment of the ration is taste, the researchers then began to study and research those sensory characteristics that determine the threshold of acceptability. This laid the foundation for building rules and methodologies for measuring sensory acceptability (Pulvirenti and De Giorgio, 2017).

In 1975, the Institute of Food Technologist (IFT) accepted the definition of Sensory Analysis as follows: "a scientific method used to awaken, measure, analyse and interpret those responses to products that are the outcome of perception by the senses of sight, smell, touch, taste and hearing" (Stone and Sidel, 1993).

This scientific technique has been gaining great momentum in recent years as its results are reliable and meaningful, thanks also to the great professional training of analysts, who must know statistics, psychology, marketing, chemistry and biochemistry in addition to sensory analysis techniques.

Sensory evaluation methods today comprise a group of established and verbalised measurement techniques used in both industry and research centres, many of which we now consider standard procedures derived from the experience of the analysts who developed them over the past 50 years. (Pagliarini, 2021)

More and more companies are introducing the use of sensory analysis to solve some of the shortcomings that relying on a single person creates. Firstly, there is the thorny issue that these experts may change companies and thus no longer provide the service of a corporate 'chef'. In addition, there is the risk that the sensory quality created by one person may meet only a portion of consumers. The use of a large panel, on the other hand, gives the possibility of potentially meeting the tastes of a very large portion of consumers. The use of specific panels also makes it possible to assess specific sensory characteristics for products aimed at a particular segment of the population (consumers with coeliac disease, the elderly, children, etc.). Panel assessment can, therefore, anticipate consumer opinions and thus the acceptability of the product itself.

Food analysis is important for quality control, studying shelf life, defining characteristics and describing products.

Therefore, sensory analysis is not new in the food industry, but its application as a fundamental tool for new product development and quality control has not always received worthy recognition and acclaim. This seems to be largely due to a lack of awareness of what it can bring to product research, development and marketing, and a concern that this 'too academic' principle is impractical (Pagliarini 2021)

2.1 The stimulus

A stimulus is any chemical or physical activator capable of causing a response in a receptor. Sensory receptors are specialised in the recognition of only one class of stimuli, which can be optical, mechanical, thermal and chemical.

Modality	Receptor	Receptor type	Organ	Stimulus
Vision	• rods and cones	• electromagnetic	• retina	• light
Hearing	• auditory hair cells	• mechanoreceptor	• organ of Corti	• vibration
Olfaction	• olfactory nerve endings	• chemoreceptor	• individual neurons	• airborne chemicals
Taste	• taste cells	• chemoreceptor	• taste bud	• food chemicals
Touch (a few examples)	• Pacinian corpuscles • free nerve endings • temperature receptors	• mechanoreceptor • nociceptor • thermoreceptor	• skin	• pressure • pain • temperature

Figure 2. Sensory receptor types (image source: www.lifeeducationpoint.com)

These physical activators stimulate the senses of sight, hearing and touch, while chemical activators stimulate the senses of taste and smell.

When an external stimulus (distant stimulus) makes contact with a receptor, it is immediately converted into an electrical signal (proximal stimulus) through the process of transduction. This process creates sensations that are felt at the cortical level. The place where the electrical impulses are decoded, collected and processed is the brain, which, through basic cognitive processes and dynamic psychological processes, organises the electrical impulses. This process is called perception. (Pagliarini 2021)

There are measurable thresholds that play a fundamental role in the creation of sensation:

- Absolute threshold of perception (SP):
indicates the minimum amount of energy that needs to be reached to cause a sensation. Below this threshold, stimulation does not produce adequate electrical impulses.
- Sensation Threshold (SR):
indicates the minimum amount of energy that must be reached to provoke a recognisable and identifiable sensation.
- Threshold Difference (SD):
represents the positive or negative energy difference that produces a perceptible increase or decrease in the intensity of the sensation.

Schematically we can summarise the stimulation-perception process as follows:

Figure 3. Stimulation-perception process (image source: www.lifeeducationpoint.com)

2.2 Anatomy and physiology of five senses

Sensory analysis utilises five sensory organs. It is important to know the anatomy, physiology and limitations of our sensory organs and receptors to better understand the results obtained and the entire sensory analysis process.

2.2.1 The vision

The main organ responsible for the functioning of vision is the eye. The eye is a complex organ comprising structures necessary for the passage of light rays and the conversion of light quanta into nerve energy (transmission) (Bortolami et al., 2009). It is all about light reflecting from an object, striking the cornea, passing through the aqueous humour and humour to the vitreous and then the retina, where the actual, smaller, inverted image is formed. The corneal crystalline aqueous complex (ocular refractive system) acts as an extremely powerful positive lens allowing images to focus on the retinal surface (Saraux et al., 1984). The receptors, rods and cones, stimulated by light, produce electrical nerve impulses that, through transduction, transmit the optic nerve to the brain. The characteristics that our eyes allow us to perceive are shape, size and colour. This last aspect is perhaps the most influential as it is closely linked to product quality.

Figure 6. Eye anatomy (La Valle, 2023)

2.2.2 The smell

Smell is the second sense, after sight, that we use to analyse food. This sense can boast two different types of awareness depending on the channel involved:

- Orthonasal: this is the external sensory system through which we perceive fragrance by breathing directly through the nose.
- Retronasal: is the internal sensory system that perceives flavour (combination of taste and smell). The product is introduced into the oral cavity and is subjected to the action of the tongue and teeth, allowing the release of volatile molecules. The olfactory epithelium is thus stimulated indirectly.

There are two conditions without which olfaction would not be perceptible; the first is that the molecules are volatile and the second is that a minimum threshold of molecules reaching the olfactory epithelium is reached. If these conditions are met, the receptors will capture and recognise the molecule, transmit the signal to the olfactory bulb and finally transmit the signal to the right hemisphere of the brain. The threshold of odour perception is directly proportional to the degree of volatility of the molecule and indirectly proportional to the degree of solubility. There is no such obvious specificity between receptors and olfactory molecules (Pagliarini, 2021).

Olfactory molecules belong to many types of chemical compounds: hydrocarbons, alcohols, carbonyl compounds, lactones, esters, ethers, phenols, etc. In sensory analysis, it is very important to take odour habituation tendencies into account. When olfactory receptors are subjected to prolonged stimulation with the same volatile molecule, they tend to become habituated and respond less and less until the odour is no longer perceptible.

Figure 7. Nose anatomy (Jellinek, 1985)

2.2.3 The taste

The entire oral cavity allows the taste, aroma and texture of food to be analysed. The tongue is the organ most involved in taste perception and is a musculoskeletal organ containing sensory organs and taste buds. The tongue has a remarkable tactile sensitivity and on its dorsal surface there are a significant number of reliefs of various shapes and sizes, called papillae.

The papillae are of different types and are located in specific areas of the mouth (Figure 8A):

- **Filiform:** contains no taste buds and has a tactile function. They are located in the central part of the tongue;
- **Fungiform:** mainly present on the tip and back of the tongue, containing between 2 and taste buds;
- **Blow:** present along the edge of the tongue, they contain hundreds of taste buds;
- **Circle:** has an inverted V shape, located at the back of the tongue and contains hundreds of taste buds;

The taste buds, made up of epithelial cells, are ovoid masses located within the epithelial thickness of the taste papilla (Fig. 8B).

Figura 8. A) Position of the papillae on the tongue B) Structure of the taste buds (Jackson, 2000)

The aromatic substances present in food and transported by saliva enter the taste buds through a channel and allow the release of electrical signals that stimulate the taste nerve to send sensory taste signals to the brain. The taste buds, are also found on the soft palate, together with the pharynx and epiglottis, are the areas responsible for taste sensation.

The tongue is naturally very rich both intrinsic and extrinsic muscles receive motor innervation from the hypoglossal nerve (cranial nerve IX). Much richer sensory innervation is provided by the lingual,

glossopharyngeal and cranial laryngeal nerves (Bortolami et al., 2012). The anatomical structures responsible for taste are able to perceive countless different chemical molecules, but give us only five taste sensations to respond to, the basic tastes: sweet, salty, sour, bitter and umami (Chaudari and Roper, 2010). This second basic flavour was identified in 1908 by Professor Ikeda of the University of Tokyo, through his research on the composition of kombu seaweed. 'Umami' comes from the Japanese word 'umai' meaning 'delicious' and its sensation is stimulated by monosodium glutamate (L-glutamate). Recent studies seem to show that fat, or rather the fatty acids that make it up, can also be considered one of the basic tastes (Proserpio et al., 2016).

Until the 1980s, it was thought that basic tastes were perceived more in a specific area of the tongue. Today, however, it is believed that the sense of taste is widespread (Guyton, 1980) and recent studies have demonstrated this through research on language distribution. The old maps of language regions are no longer valid.

Other tastes are classified as basic: metallic, pungent and astringent. In fact, they no longer exist today and we know that they are the senses of taste, i.e. the olfactory and tactile sensations (Mouthfeels). Saliva is the main factor in the taste response: it is the means of transporting taste molecules to the receptors and is a taste regulator capable of blocking acidity due to substances it contains such as sodium and carbonate.

The taste organs detect flavours through a transduction mechanism. Sweet, bitter and umami tastes utilise molecular transduction mechanisms mediated by taste receptors linked to G-proteins, a mechanism referred to as 'key blocking', while salty and sour tastes are directly related to membrane ion channels (Jackson, 2000)

Figure 9. A) Older concept of concentration of specific taste receptors. B) Newer concept of clusters of blends of taste receptors (Thomas et al. 2022)

There are significant inter-individual differences in taste perception and food preferences, due to many factors such as genetics (variations in genes coding for receptors), socio-cultural background, etc.

However, it is good to know that reactions to hedonism and basic tastes are similar across cultures. In fact, studies have found that responses to the fundamental tastes sweet, bitter and salty are present from the moment an individual is born, and responses to salty develop within a few months (Pagliarini, 2021).

2.2.4 The touch

Touch involves different anatomical parts: fingers, lips, tongue, through very sensitive receptors (they can distinguish particles with a particle size of up to 20-25 μ) identified in:

- tactile receptors: located on the skin, the mucosa of the oral cavity and the pharynx. They obtain information regarding particle size and structure;
- Muscle receptors: located in the jaw and teeth. They obtain coherent information;

The information we can obtain is: shape, size and texture of the analysed product. Texture is the tactile sensation we perceive in the oral cavity: astringency, viscosity and greasiness (Pagliarini, 2002).

There are chemesthetic sensations, chemically induced sensations: spicy, refreshing, warming, irritating. These are sensations associated with the stimulation of the trigeminal nerve fibres. We have seen that other taste sensations were once associated with basic tastes but have turned out to be tactile sensations: astringency, chemically produced tactile sensations and metallicity.

In particular, astringency is a “complex sensation that combines three distinct aspects: dryness of the jaws, irritation of the oral tissues and perception of “ripples” in the cheek and facial muscles” (Lee et Lawless, 1991).

Figure 10. Skin anatomy (Ghèhin 2023)

2.2.5 The hearing

The ear has three components: the outer ear, the middle ear and the inner ear. The outer ear consists of the auricle, or earlobe, and the external auditory canal.

The auricle also has the task of protecting the eardrum from damage. Sweat glands in the ear canal form earwax.

The middle ear is an air-filled space located in the temporal bone of the skull. Air pressure in this space through the Eustachian tube flows into the nasopharynx or the back of the throat and nose.

There are three small bones, or ossicles, which are located adjacent to the tympanic membrane. The malleus incuses and stapes are attached, like a chain, to the tympanic membrane and convert the sound waves that vibrate the membrane into mechanical vibrations of the three bones. The stirrup fills the oval window, which is the connection to the inner ear.

The ear is sensitive and responds to sounds of very low intensity, to vibrations that are just above the natural random movement of air molecules.

For this, the air pressure on both sides of the tympanic membrane must be equal. The Eustachian tube provides the means for pressure equalisation.

The middle ear cavity is quite small and the mastoid air cells act as an air reservoir to cushion the effects of pressure change. The outer ear and the middle ear serve to amplify the sound signal. The sense of hearing is involved in the evaluation of food for all vibration-related attributes: during biting, humans produce vibrations that can be associated with attributes such as crunchiness (biscuits or crisps) (Vickers, 1991).

Figure 11. Ear anatomy (image source: www.studyblue.com)

2.3 The laboratory

According to the definition of the dedicated standard, a sensory analysis laboratory is "a place where evaluation by examiners takes place because it facilitates evaluation that is not influenced by physical and psychological factors." (ISO 8589:2007). It is very important that there are no distracting factors such as unusual lights, noises or smells that could mislead the panel. Also according to ISO standards, there are two essential and other recommended areas for carrying out sensory analysis. The sensory analysis laboratory must be located in a quiet place. Acoustic, thermal, visual and olfactory neutrality is essential.

The essential requirements are:

- a separate test space (test chamber) is required; it is the place where the sensory evaluation is conducted. The individual evaluation space, or booth, is a space used for tasting samples. As seen above, this area is located near the sample preparation area but separated from it. Tasting booths are designed to accommodate one jury member in a limited space. Each booth should be equipped with: desk, sample, sink, cleaning products, feedback form or digital information collection device, pen. The only connection between the booth and the sample preparation area is a slot for dispensing products, through which the judges can interact with the panel leader without disturbing the rest of the panel. The slots used to introduce the object to be assessed into the booth must be equipped with watertight doors to prevent the spread of odours that might emanate from the sample preparation area.

- sample preparation area, separated and equipped with a fume hood. It should be a kitchen equipped with electrical appliances, utensils, glassware and analytical instruments. The sample preparation area or kitchen should be adjacent to the tasting area. The kitchen must be ventilated to prevent odours from sample preparation lingering in the air, and the kitchen materials must be easy to clean.
- a collective space in which various activities such as judge preparation and collective sessions between judges and panel leader take place; this part must also be close to the sample preparation area and must be isolated from this area. Part of this space can be used as an office and used for analysing the collected data.

Figure 12. The tasting booth and plan of a sensory analysis laboratory (ISO 8589:2007)

2.4 Methods of sensory analysis

2.4.1 Affective methods

The perceptual method answers the following question: "Which is the product that consumers most love?"

For a company, this question is very important because it may become the key to the commercial success of the product. The individual's level of satisfaction with a product is personal and difficult to measure. Perceptual methods help us understand the mechanism of subjective preference: they are used when it is necessary to determine the degree of acceptance of a product made of consumers and whether some products are rated more or less than others. The control panel used is the consumers themselves.

Panels of at least 100 people are often used. A large number of judges is essential to minimise variation in subjective perceptions of product quality, which are inevitably influenced by factors related to personal experience, physiology, culture and genetics. The execution of emotion tests uses two main methods: measuring preference and measuring acceptability.

In measuring preference, the judge must make a choice, which is why he or she expresses his or her preference based on a comparison of two or more products. However, to measure acceptability, it is not necessary to compare but to evaluate each product and express satisfaction using a scale.

2.4.2 Discriminants methods

The discriminants method can be useful in several cases:

- During training, to determine which panelists are most sensitive;
- During sensory testing, to distinguish the current substrate from other similar substrates;
- Quality control or quality assurance;

These methods are used when it is necessary to assess whether a difference exists between two products. If this difference exists, we can consider more specifically the degree of difference, the quality of the difference and the extent to which this difference influences the preference of one product over the other.

The triangle test is described according to ISO 4120:2021. This International Standard describes a procedure for determining whether there is a perceivable sensory difference or similarity between samples of two products.

This method is a forced-choice procedure. The number of panel components is chosen according to the sensitivity of the test, which is statistically determined by the values chosen for the following parameters:

- risk α : is the probability of concluding that there is a difference when in fact there is not;
- Risk β : is the probability of concluding that there is no difference when in fact it is;
- pd: percentage of judges able to distinguish between the products;

If the aim of the test is to prove that there is a difference between the samples, the value of α will be lower than β on the contrary.

The triangle test is so called because in the first version proposed, three samples arranged at the vertices of a triangle are presented. Nowadays, samples are presented on a single line and were on the left ending on the right. The examiners are informed of the presence of another sample and asked to identify it.

Therefore, a choice is necessary, as in the case the case of the paired test, which does not include the answer "no difference". The judge must administer the test and report the answers according to the prescribed form. If the judge cannot determine the difference, he/she must still mark an answer and state in the comments that this answer was deduced by supposition, if not, indeed, by guessing. Tests should not be repeated to avoid increasing the likelihood of errors.

The panellist should not be able to tell the difference through the presentation of the samples. Therefore, the samples should kept at the same temperature, should not show any differences in colour and/or surface appearance , and finally must be presented in the same quantity and in identical containers.

We do not use statistical treatments for discriminant tests, whereas but use contingency tables, depending on the number of cells taken and the number of correct answers, the probability of A being distinguished from B or not.

Figure 13. Triangle test tray (Stone e Sidel, 1993).

According to ISO 5495:2005 the test in pairs was chosen to investigate whether there is a perceptible difference in the intensity of the descriptor between two samples. The two samples are presented together or consecutively.

The number of panel members is chosen as in the triangle test, based on the choice of test sensitivity (using the α , β and p_d risks mentioned above). However, a panel of 30 to 32 judges may be recommended if we want to demonstrate a difference in intensity, while it must be doubled if we want to demonstrate similarity of products. Combined tests can only be used if there is uniformity between the products and what not allows for quantitative but only qualitative feedback.

ISO 10399:2017 specifies the duo-trio test, defining it as a test method to determine whether there is a sensory difference or similarity between samples of two products. The panel is assigned a reference sample R and two additional samples to be compared with R. They are asked to define the model using the R model.

The number of panel members selected for the paired test depends on the choice of test sensitivity, as for a triangle test. However, if one wishes to demonstrate differences, a panel of 32-36 judges may be advisable, whereas, ones more, this number should be doubled if one wishes to demonstrate similarities between products.

The evaluation of the results uses statistical methods similar to the test in pair, which is likely to give a correct answer in 50 per cent of the cases.

ISO 6658:2017 specifies the two out of five test, which is used to determine whether there is a discernible sensory difference between two samples, especially when the number of evaluations available is small (10 to 20). This is an efficient method because the probability of correctly identifying two out of five samples is 1 out of 10, whereas in the triangle test it is 1 out of 3 and in the other two tests it is 1 out of 2.

However, this is a test that strains the senses and is therefore mainly used in the cosmetics and tactile fields. In the food industry, it is mainly used for vision-related tests. The judge is handed a tray with five identical samples and asked to identify two identical samples.

2.4.3 Descriptive methods

The methods described so far are the most comprehensive and complex. The reference standard is ISO 13299:2016, which provides guidance on the overall process of developing sensory profiles. Sensory profiles can be determined for any product or sample that can be assessed by sight, smell, taste, touch or hearing. The descriptive method is based on the proposition that the sensory impact of a product is produced by all identifiable sensory attributes. These are called 'descriptors'. All sensory descriptors fall into different categories: appearance, smell, taste, tactile, mouthfeel and texture, each with its own intensity, thus representing sensory characteristics. Descriptive analysis therefore involves all sensations (smell, taste, sight, touch) but can also help to evaluate only certain aspects such as texture, colour or other aspects.

Therefore, the descriptive method is used to describe a particular product or, after highlighting the differences between two products derived from the results of a discrimination test, is used to study the qualitative difference between the two products. It is used in industry to compare or understand differences between product variations in business processes.

The resulting sensory profile is presented graphically for immediate understanding. The mean values represent the intensities of the descriptors placed on unstructured scales arranged in a spider's web pattern on the map. The mean values are then concatenated through the segments. The combination of broken segments forming a star shape (with as many vertices as the number of descriptors) is called a spider graph.

There are four steps in descriptive analysis (Pagliarini, 2002):

- Qualitative analysis: this consists of identifying the descriptive terms of the sensory properties of the products. A “vocabulary” of sensory descriptors must be created;
- Panel calibration: the panel leader chooses the most appropriate rating scale, at the ends of which the minimum and maximum values are indicated;
- Quantitative analysis: the samples are analysed by panelists, who assess the intensity of each descriptor according to the rating scale chosen by the panel leader;
- Validation, data processing and presentation: Statistical analysis to the interpretation of the information derived from the data. Presentation of the differences between products according to their sensory properties;

The choice of descriptors and the consequent use of correct terminology is of fundamental importance. Three distinct alternative or integrable approaches can be used, listed below (Villa, 2013):

- consulting the available bibliography (official terminologies exist for many products);
- establish the most appropriate terminology through round tables attended by designated assessors under the coordination of the panel leader;
- through the use of specially prepared samples, terms can be identified and selected according to the method indicated in ISO 11035:1994;

To minimise individual differences, a panel of 8-12 trained judges is required. The training conditions of the examiners are crucial for the descriptive method, because only this panel can describe minimal differences between samples. An untrained panel can still be used in descriptive tests using the 'free-choice profiling' method. Free choice profiling (FCP), developed in 1984 by Williams and Langron (1984), is a sensory analysis method that can be performed by untrained panels. Participants only need to be able to use the scale and be frequent consumers of the evaluated product (Perez et al., 2007).

The sensory method involves a series of meetings to establish which descriptors make up the web of the evaluated product and with what intensity.

The first meeting is held to explain in detail the purpose of the analysis and ascertain the suitability of the panel of judges (all judges must be trained and must be sensory consumers of the product under analysis). A questionnaire may be administered to test the judges' eating habits.

During the first sessions, a quantitative analysis of the descriptions will be carried out. In subsequent sessions (at least four), once the common vocabulary of sensory descriptors has been identified, the judges are presented with several representative samples, including the one whose sensory profile is to be described.

These samples must be served in such a way as not to generate evaluative deviations from the nature of the presentation, so they must be offered at the same temperature and coded with three random digits. The sessions should be replicated, if possible, on different days but at the same time and randomising the order in which the samples are served.

Once the judges have completed their evaluation, the response values are analysed using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) to distribute the scores between the different sections considering the overall variability of the sensory data. There are essentially three sources of variation: sample, examiner, session (Pagliarini, 2002).

In ANOVA, it is possible to choose to evaluate a single factor (sample effect or test effect) or to evaluate several factors (examiner effect and test effect) Finally, the mean data of each descriptor obtained with the ANOVA statistical method are subjected to principal component analysis (PCA), which allows the graphical representation of a multidimensional space with a limited number of

dimensions (principal components) (Todeschini, 1998). The PCA graph further explains the variance of the original data.

In the late 1940s, the first evaluation method with a group of trained judges was created, called Flavor Profile[®] (Caul, 1957).

Subsequently, in the 1970 was created a far more refined method, known as the Texture Profile, to quantify the texture of foods, just as the Flavour Profile[®] had permitted the quantification of flavour properties (Szezesniak et al., 2002).

Subsequently, other approaches were proposed for the descriptive analysis of foods. In 1974, the method called Quantitative Descriptive Analysis (QDA[®]) expanded the description possibilities, in terms of attributes, to the entire sensory perception, and not only to the taste and texture (Stone et al., 2012).

3. THE JUDGES

One becomes a taster, but to be able to 'say it tastes like spinach' one has to follow a learning and practice programme defined by ISO standards. One can easily understand that the selection and screening of the next candidate plays a vital role in obtaining adequate sensory responses and therefore must be done carefully. Therefore, the goal of candidate selection is to assess the skills and capabilities of each candidate in order to select those individuals with the best ability to perceive, measure and differentiate the sensory characteristics of the product under consideration.

When I started my PhD course in the Department of Veterinary Medical Sciences, there was no trained panel. During the first year of my PhD I worked on the construction of the working tool, that is the panel itself.

The process of selecting and training candidates to become judges is explained below.

We have seen that the judge is the analytical tool of sensory science and must therefore be calibrated. ISO 8586:2023 describes the general guidelines for the selection, training and supervision of selectors and sensory assessors, as shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14. General guidelines for the selection, training and monitoring of selected assessors and expert sensory assessors (ISO 8586:2023)

Depending on the choice of method applied for the sensory analysis, the team led by the panel leader may include several components:

- they are experienced reviewers. The groups consist of 6 to 12 members;
- judges are selected after sensory training. The group consists of 20 to 50 judges;
- judges with no experience in sensory analysis, generally consumers, are employed in numbers above 100

There is a panel leader in the group. This role is assigned to a person with a typical university education, who must possess good organisational skills and have an in-depth knowledge of statistics and psychology. Finally, the workshop facilitator must always consider the fact that individuals tend not to be fully aware of the potential of their sensory abilities (Amerine et al., 1965; Carpenter et al., 2000).

Knowledge of psychology is particularly useful in the early stages of selection; as mentioned, individuals are not fully aware of their perceptual abilities and, to avoid putting candidates in awkward situations after making mistakes, it is best to number the questions gradually, skipping the candidate's name.

The panel leader is in charge of organising the evaluation sessions, leading the tastings, collecting data and compiling statistics.

Candidates should meet from 11:00 to 13:00 or 16:00 to 17:30. These times are designed and recommended because candidates have a moderate appetite stimulation, so it is important to remember to refrain from eating and drinking at least half an hour before the start of the test to avoid overheating.

Samples should be served randomly, should be sealed and clearly identified and finally, a maximum of six matrices at a time should be tested together to avoid sensory fatigue.

When recruiting potential candidates, it is important to administer background questionnaires (Figure 15A) (Zammuner, 1998). After the first general part of the face-to-face and/or oral interview, the second phase allows us to analyse in more detail which foods the candidate prefers to consume (and how often) (Figure 15B).

It is necessary to know the following personal information:

- General abilities of the candidate;
- Attitude towards matrices;
- Availability of time;
- Smoker or non-smoker: smokers may join the panel, but should be reminded not to smoke for at least 30 minutes before the test;
- Personal hygiene: remind candidates not to wear perfume;
- Punctuality;

The same substances at different concentrations are placed in each glass and the candidate must rank these concentrations in ascending order by recording the results on a questionnaire given by the evaluator. Several glasses may have the same concentration to prevent competitors from ordering glasses by deduction.

After completing these two tests, candidates will complete the taste recognition phase and become familiar with the different types of thresholds.

Taste	Composition
Reference solution	30 mM KCl, 0.3 mM tartaric acid
Saltiness	300 mM KCl, 0.3 mM tartaric acid
Sourness	30 mM KCl, 3mM tartaric acid
Umami	10 mM monosodium glutamate
Bitterness (+)	0.1 mM Quinine-HCl
Bitterness (-)	0.01 vol% iso-alpha acid
Astringency	0.05 wt% tannic acid
Sweetness	1 M Sucrose

Figure 16. Reference solutions for basic taste evaluation (Tahara et al. 2013)

The ISO 5496:2006 standard specifies methods for olfactory training, with a distinction between direct olfactory methods and retronasal olfactory methods.

There are three different ways to conduct a session for direct odour:

- Smell assessment in the bottle: bottles were handed to the candidates, who were sniffed and asked to keep their mouth closed during the session.
- Assessing smell by means of an olfactory strip: these strips were given to the candidates to shake gently under their nostrils and sniff them with their mouths closed;
- Smell assessment using capsules: give the candidates each capsule to open and close their mouths for sniffing.

As regards the methods of assessing the retronasal odour, we have two methods:

- Evaluation of the gas phase: the solution must first be prepared, then the solution is placed in a glass and covered with a thin film. The beakers are presented to the candidates, who have to pierce the film with a straw in order to suck out the gas;

- Assess by drinking the aqueous solution: prepare the solution and place it in a small cup with a perforated lid, insert a straw. Handing the cups to the competitor, the competitor must inhale the liquid and exhale through the nose and close the mouth.

Taste or odour	Material	Chemical Abstracts Service (CAS) No.	Concentration in water at room temperature g/l	Concentration in ethanol ^a at room temperature g/l
Lemon, fresh	Citral (C ₁₀ H ₁₆ O)	5392-40-5	—	1 × 10 ⁻³
Vanilla	Vanillin (C ₈ H ₈ O ₃)	121-33-5	—	1 × 10 ⁻³
Thyme	Thymol (C ₁₀ H ₁₄ O)	89-83-8	—	5 × 10 ⁻⁴
Floral, lily of the valley, jasmine	Benzyl acetate (C ₉ H ₁₀ O ₂)	140-11-4	—	1 × 10 ⁻³

Figure 17. Reference solutions for odour evaluation (ISO 8586:2023)

The panel leader can assess the level of training of the candidates by comparing the percentage of correct answers given by each of them with the percentage of minimum answers required to become part of a panel. (Amerine et al. 1965; ISO 16820:2019)

Method considered	Minimum percentage of correct answers
Fundamental taste identification method	100
Threshold method	80
Odour recognition method	80
Test in pairs	70
Triangle test	70
Sorting method for intensity of fundamental tastes	60
Sorting method for colour recognition	90

Figure 18. Minimum percentages to be considered when assessing the adequacy of training (designed by Martina Magnani)

After the entire selection and training process, a sensory panel is created that is ready to get to work on the matrices presented to it.

Below are the publications of the projects in which the selected and trained panel participated.

CHAPTER

4.

EFFECT OF DIFFERENT INCLUSION LEVELS OF DEFATTED *HERMETIA ILLUCENS* LARVAE MEAL ON FILLET QUALITY OF GILTHEAD SEA BREAM (*SPARUS AURATA*).

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Abstract

In recent years, insect meal has attracted increasing interest as an innovative protein source to replace fish meal in feed formulation due to its valuable nutritional profile. This research aimed to compare the effects of different dietary inclusion levels (5, 10, and 15%) of *Hermetia illucens* (HI) larvae meal on *Sparus aurata* (initial weight: 98.6±0.6 g) sensorial, technological, and nutritional fillets quality. Fish were fed experimental diets over 113 days. Results showed that the inclusion of defatted HI larvae meal did not induce off-flavours in gilthead sea bream fillets. No significant differences were found in appearance, mouthfeels, and texture, while a difference emerged in the trait 'cooked chicken breast' for odour and flavour characteristics. Moreover, fillets' quality traits and proximate composition analyses performed did not show significant differences between the treatments. The fillets' fatty acid content showed that higher inclusion of HI meal leads to higher saturated fatty acids (SFAs) content, while no significant difference in polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs) was observed among treatments. Results have a positive implication as dietary HI did not negatively affect the fatty acids composition or quality of sea bream fillets.

Keywords: sensory profile, fillet technological quality, insect meal, fish meal substitution, fillet nutritional quality.

4.1 Introduction

In recent decades, the demand for sustainably produced proteins for human consumption has grown so considerably that the current protein production would have to double by 2050. This poses a huge challenge considering that the European Union (EU) still has a deficit for high-quality protein materials (30-50%). Consequently, the great protein demand is now largely met by imported proteins with severe concerns regarding feed and food security and the general competitiveness of the EU (FEFAC, 2018).

Considering the increasing standard of living and the fast growth of the world population, there is a rising demand for seafood (Alfiko *et al.*, 2022). Today the aquaculture industry plays a key role as a world-wide supplier of high-protein quality products, and farmed fish products are expected to rise from 114.5 million tons in 2018 to 201 million tons by 2030 (FAO, 2020). Fish nutritional requirements, particularly for carnivorous fish, are quite high in terms of quality and quantity of protein. For this reason, fish meal (FM) has been traditionally considered the best protein source in feed formulation (Kok *et al.*, 2020). However, FM is a limited available product (Hidalgo *et al.*,

2022), and finding alternative protein sources that are sustainable, circular, and environmentally friendly, needs to be urgently addressed (Colombo *et al.*, 2022).

Promising alternative protein sources, such as insect meal, are already eyeing market adoption. Among the positive aspects of insect meal utilization, its application as a sustainable aquafeed ingredient is a very interesting topic, especially for its high nutritional value. As such, insects present a high protein content that varies according to the species from 25% to 75% (Colombo *et al.*, 2022). They have valid amino acids (AAs) profiles in good correlation with fish dietary requirements (NRC,2011; Henry *et al.*, 2015). Additionally, insects are rich in lipids, vitamins (e.g., pyridoxine, riboflavin, folic acid, and vitamin B12), and minerals (potassium, calcium, iron, magnesium, zinc, and selenium) (Henry *et al.*, 2015).

In particular, *Hermetia illucens* (HI) has attracted increasing interest both as an alternative protein source to replace FM and as an ingredient with an excellent nutritional profile. It contains about 35–46% (DM) protein with an essential AAs profile similar to that of FM with the exception of lysine which may be deficient in some insect species (Fisher *et al.*, 2020). HI lipid content ranges between 15-49%, depending on the larvae's diet. Specifically, some studies have shown that by altering insect larval feed intake, the fatty acids (FAs) profile of larvae can be manipulated (Barroso *et al.*, 2017; Ewald *et al.*, 2020; Liu *et al.*, 2017). Larval age may also have an important effect, with an increase in saturated fatty acids (SFAs) and a decrease in unsaturated fatty acids in older larvae (Liu *et al.*, 2017). Also, the HI larvae lipid content varies whether the defatting process was done or not (Huyben *et al.*, 2019).

HI meal has been recently utilised as a protein source in fish feed with the purpose of investigating its potential effects on growth performance, feed utilization efficiency, fish welfare, and health (Abdel-Latif *et al.*, 2021; Abu Bakar *et al.*, 2021; Bruni *et al.*, 2020a, 2020b; Caimi *et al.*, 2021, 2020b, 2020a; Xu *et al.*, 2020). Sensory analysis and more specifically Quantitative Descriptive Analysis (QDA) is a valid method for providing information on the sensory properties of food. Several studies utilised QDA in order to investigate relationships between fish flavour, fillet texture, and fillet nutritional profile (Izquierdo *et al.*, 2005). Studies conducted on Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*) and Rainbow trout fillets (*O. mykiss*) did not show sensory significant differences between diets despite a high percentage of HI inclusion in substitution of FM (Lock *et al.*, 2016; St-Hilaire *et al.*, 2007).

Furthermore, it should be considered that diet ingredients influence the fillet technological properties, with special reference to muscle pH which plays a crucial role in assuring a proper level of Water Holding Capacity (WHC) to fish fillets (Iaconisi *et al.*, 2018).

In this study, sea bream (*Sparus aurata*) was chosen because is the species of major interest in Mediterranean aquaculture. Although several studies have been conducted on sea bream fed diets containing HI in substitution of FM (Bosi *et al.*, 2021; Carvalho *et al.*, 2023; Fabrikov *et al.*, 2021, 2020; Mastoraki *et al.*, 2022; Oteri *et al.*, 2022; Panteli *et al.*, 2021; Pulido *et al.*, 2022), to the best of our knowledge, only a few studies tested low and moderate HI inclusion (5-15%) (Carvalho *et al.*, 2023; Oteri *et al.*, 2022), and no studies investigated on nutritional, technological, and sensory fillet quality at the same time. The present study aimed to assess the effects of different inclusion levels of HI larvae meal on the nutritional, technological, and sensory quality of sea bream fillets.

4.2 Materials and methods

4.2.1 Experimental Diets

Four experimental diets were produced via extrusion technology by Sparos Lda (Olhão, Portugal) with a different inclusion level of HI larvae meal (0% CTRL, 5% HI5, 10% HI10, and 15% HI15) in substitution for FM on a protein basis. All powder ingredients were mixed accordingly to the target formulation in a double-helix mixer (model 500 L, TGC Extrusion, France) and ground (below 400 µm) in a micro pulverizer hammer mill (model SH1, Hosokawa-Alpine, Germany). Diets (pellet size: 4.5 mm) were manufactured with a twin-screw extruder (model BC45, CLEXTRAL, France). Extrusion conditions: feeder rate (78-83 kg/h), screw speed (256-267 rpm), water addition (340 ml/min), temperature barrel 1 (34-37 °C), temperature barrel 3 (109-114 °C). Extruded pellets were dried in a vibrating fluid bed dryer (model DR100, TGC Extrusion, France) for a target moisture level of approximately 8%. After cooling, oils were added by vacuum coating (model PG-10VCLAB, Dinnissen, The Netherlands). Coating conditions: pressure (700 mbar); spraying time under vacuum (approximately 90 seconds), return to atmospheric pressure (120 seconds). Immediately after coating, diets were packed in sealed.

Insect meal was produced from black soldier fly larvae reared on organic substrates by the company Mutatec (France). Diets' ingredients and their proximate composition are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Ingredients and proximate composition of the four experimental diets provided to sea bream (*Sparus aurata*) over 113 days. Three diets contained different inclusion levels of *Hermetia illucens* (HI) larvae meal in substitution of fish meal (FM).

<i>Experimental diets</i>				
<i>Ingredients (%)</i>	CTRL	HI5	HI10	HI15
¹ FM	22.0	18.1	14.1	10.1
² <i>Hermetia illucens</i> meal	0.00	5.01	10.0	15.0
Wheat flour	9.82	8.47	7.12	5.79
Wheat gluten meal	3.07	3.08	3.08	3.09
Soybean meal	11.4	11.5	11.5	11.5
Maize gluten meal	26.4	26.4	26.5	26.5
Soy protein Concentrate	13.2	13.2	13.2	13.3
Rapeseed oil	7.52	6.89	6.37	5.76
Fish oil	3.22	3.71	4.09	4.56
DL-Methionine	0.26	0.30	0.33	0.36
HCl Lysine	0.26	0.33	0.41	0.50
Taurine	0.22	0.24	0.26	0.27
Monammonium Phosphate	0.79	1.01	1.24	1.43
Vit. C	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07
³ Premix Vitamins and Minerals	0.69	0.69	0.69	0.69
Hydrolysed shrimp protein (liquid)	1.03	1.03	1.03	1.03
<i>Proximate Composition (%)</i>				
Moisture	7.29	7.62	7.40	7.13
Crude protein	51.1	51.5	51.6	53.1
Crude fat	13.5	14.4	13.6	13.6
Ash	6.44	6.37	6.28	6.17
Crude Fiber	1.95	4.31	2.56	4.80
⁴ NFE	19.72	15.80	18.56	15.20
Crude Energy In feed (cal/g)	5249.3	5227.9	5206.5	5186.5

¹protein content in FM: 66%

²Origin: Mutatec (France). Proximate composition (g/100g): Proteins 55, Fibres10, Lipids 10, Saturated Fatty acids 6 (lauric acid 40.1%, palmitic acid 15.1%, myristic acid 8.5%), Monounsaturated fatty acids 2 (oleic acid 13.5%), Polyunsaturated fatty acids 2 (linoleic acid 12.8%), Ash 11, Gross energy (KJ/100g) 2041.

³ Vitamins and mineral premix (mg/kg diet, in vivo NSA: Portugal): vit. D 0.05 mg, vit. A 2.38 mg, vit. E 324.68 mg, inositol 158.40 mg, niacin 182.17 mg, pantothenic acid 67.69 mg, vit. B2 27.44 mg, vit. B1 27.44 mg, vit. B6 24.27 mg, folic acid 6.52 mg, vit. K 5.39 mg, biotin 0.96 mg, vit. B12 0.05 mg, choline 1314.58 mg, vit. C 250.25 mg, calcium 0.87 mg, cobalt 0.38 mg, copper 48.62 mg, iron 494.70 mg, magnesium 21.27 mg, manganese 25.89 mg, molybdate 0.97 mg, nickel 0.80 mg, phosphorus 0.51 mg, potassium 0.83 mg, sodium 0.14 mg, selenium 0.83 mg, sulfur 0.35 mg, zinc 52.67 mg.

⁴NFE (Nitrogen free extracts) (%) = 100% - (moisture + protein + lipid + ash)

CTRL= control diet; HI5= 5% of HI meal; HI10= 10% of HI; HI15= 15% of HI meal.

The composition by weight of the FAs contained in the experimental diets is shown in Table 2. Moisture content was gained by weight loss after drying samples in an oven at 105 °C overnight. Crude protein was detected as total nitrogen (N*6.25) using Kjeldahl's method in accordance with AOAC International (2010). Total lipids were obtained following the Bligh and Dyer's (1959) extraction method. Ash content was estimated by incineration in a muffle oven at 450 °C overnight. Crude energy was measured by a calorimetric bomb (Adiabatic Calorimetric Bomb Parr 1261; PARR Instrument, IL, United States). The crude fibre was determined according to EC 152/09 27/01/2009. Fatty analysis composition of diets was performed according to ISO16958:2015.

Table 2. List of fatty acids composition of the control diet and the three diets containing different inclusion levels of *Hermetia illucens* (HI) larvae meal.

¹ FAs (g/100g)	CTRL	HI5	HI10	HI15
10:0	0.0010 ± 0.00	0.006 ± 0.001	0.010 ± 0.002	0.014 ± 0.003
12:0	0.032 ± 0.006	0.083 ± 0.018	0.154 ± 0.033	0.011 ± 0.002
14:0	0.345 ± 0.053	0.412 ± 0.059	0.458 ± 0.064	0.523 ± 0.070
15:0	0.023 ± 0.004	0.024 ± 0.005	0.026 ± 0.005	0.035 ± 0.007
16:0	1.53 ± 0.18	1.67 ± 0.20	1.70 ± 0.20	1.82 ± 0.22
17:0	0.027 ± 0.005	0.030 ± 0.006	0.023 ± 0.006	0.031 ± 0.006
18:0	0.332 ± 0.052	0.363 ± 0.055	0.353 ± 0.054	0.373 ± 0.056
20:0	0.053 ± 0.011	0.065 ± 0.014	0.060 ± 0.013	0.058 ± 0.012
22:0	0.018 ± 0.004	0.026 ± 0.005	0.018 ± 0.004	0.021 ± 0.005
24:0	0.007 ± 0.001	0.014 ± 0.003	0.010 ± 0.002	0.009 ± 0.002
SFAs total	2.41 ± 0.20	2.75 ± 0.22	2.88 ± 0.22	2.96 ± 0.24
16:1 total	0.42 ± 0.84	0.49 ± 0.42	0.51 ± 0.42	0.52 ± 0.42
16:1t n-7	0.01 ± 0.42	0.01 ± 0.42	0.01 ± 0.42	0.01 ± 0.42
16:1 n-7	0.413 ± 0.059	0.479 ± 0.066	0.500 ± 0.068	0.508 ± 0.068
17:1 total	0.008 ± 0.001	0.008 ± 0.001	0.016 ± 0.002	0.016 ± 0.003
17:1 n7	0.008 ± 0.002	0.008 ± 0.002	0.009 ± 0.002	0.010 ± 0.002
18:1 total	5.22 ± 0.45	5.38 ± 0.46	4.90 ± 0.43	4.56 ± 0.40
18:1t n-9	0.017 ± 0.004	0.0010 ± 0.00	0.019 ± 0.004	0.025 ± 0.005
18:1t n-8	0.0010 ± 0.00	0.019 ± 0.004	0.0010 ± 0.00	0.0010 ± 0.00
18:1t n-7	0.0010 ± 0.00	0.057 ± 0.012	0.060 ± 0.013	0.068 ± 0.014
18:1 n-9	4.76 ± 0.44	4.90 ± 0.45	4.46 ± 0.42	4.12 ± 0.39
18:1 n-7	0.373 ± 0.056	0.394 ± 0.058	0.361 ± 0.055	0.348 ± 0.054
18:1 n-6	0.012 ± 0.002	0.013 ± 0.003	0.004 ± 0.001	0.0010 ± 0.00
20:1 total	0.136 ± 0.029	0.149 ± 0.032	0.132 ± 0.028	0.133 ± 0.028
20:1 n9	0.136 ± 0.029	0.149 ± 0.032	0.132 ± 0.028	0.133 ± 0.028
22:1 total	0.047 ± 0.007	0.059 ± 0.009	0.050 ± 0.007	0.040 ± 0.006
22:1 n11	0.022 ± 0.005	0.027 ± 0.006	0.026 ± 0.005	0.016 ± 0.003
22:1 n9	0.026 ± 0.005	0.032 ± 0.006	0.024 ± 0.005	0.025 ± 0.005
24:1 n9	0.019 ± 0.004	0.030 ± 0.006	0.016 ± 0.003	0.024 ± 0.005
MUFAs total	5.85 ± 0.61	6.12 ± 0.62	5.63 ± 0.60	5.30 ± 0.58
18:2 total	2.28 ± 0.25	2.39 ± 0.26	2.24 ± 0.25	2.13 ± 0.24
18:2c,t n6	0.013 ± 0.003	0.016 ± 0.003	0.015 ± 0.003	0.016 ± 0.003
18:2 n6	2.26 ± 0.25	2.37 ± 0.26	2.22 ± 0.25	2.11 ± 0.24
20:2 n6	0.015 ± 0.003	0.016 ± 0.003	0.017 ± 0.003	0.016 ± 0.003

¹ FAs (g/100g)	CTRL	HI5	HI10	HI15
18:3 total	0.714 ± 0.088	0.735 ± 0.090	0.655 ± 0.083	0.625 ± 0.077
18:3t,c,c n3	0.012 ± 0.003	0.015 ± 0.003	0.014 ± 0.003	0.008 ± 0.002
18:3 n6	0.007 ± 0.001	0.0010 ± 0.00	0.0010 ± 0.00	0.010 ± 0.002
18:3c,c,t n3	0.0010 ± 0.00	0.0010 ± 0.00	0.0010 ± 0.00	0.019 ± 0.004
18:3 n	0.695 ± 0.088	0.711 ± 0.090	0.641 ± 0.083	0.587 ± 0.077
20:3 total	0.011 ± 0.002	0.013 ± 0.002	0.010 ± 0.002	0.011 ± 0.002
18:4 n3	0.097 ± 0.021	0.109 ± 0.023	0.108 ± 0.023	0.107 ± 0.023
20:4 total	0.054 ± 0.012	0.060 ± 0.013	0.057 ± 0.012	0.053 ± 0.011
20:4 n6 (ARA)	0.054 ± 0.012	0.060 ± 0.013	0.057 ± 0.012	0.053 ± 0.011
20:5 n3(EPA)	0.696 ± 0.088	0.83 ± 0.11	0.783 ± 0.098	0.807 ± 0.100
22:5 total	0.080 ± 0.015	0.100 ± 0.019	0.082 ± 0.016	0.083 ± 0.017
22:5 n6	0.015 ± 0.003	0.017 ± 0.004	0.012 ± 0.003	0.008 ± 0.002
22:5 n3	0.065 ± 0.014	0.083 ± 0.018	0.069 ± 0.015	0.074 ± 0.016
22:6 n3(DHA)	0.389 ± 0.057	0.456 ± 0.064	0.354 ± 0.054	0.355 ± 0.054
PUFAs > C20	0.475 ± 0.059	0.566 ± 0.067	0.440 ± 0.057	0.448 ± 0.057
PUFAs total	4.34 ± 0.29	4.72 ± 0.31	4.31 ± 0.29	4.20 ± 0.28
Total n-3	1.96 ± 0.14	2.22 ± 0.16	1.98 ± 0.14	1.97 ± 0.14
Total n- 6	2.39 ± 0.25	2.52 ± 0.26	2.34 ± 0.25	2.23 ± 0.24
n- 3/n- 6	0.82 ± 0.10	0.88 ± 0.11	0.85 ± 0.11	0.88 ± 0.12
PUFAs/MUFAs	0.742 ± 0.092	0.771 ± 0.093	0.766 ± 0.097	0.79 ± 0.10
PUFAs/SFAs	1.80 ± 0.19	1.72 ± 0.18	1.50 ± 0.16	1.42 ± 0.15

¹ FAs = Fatty acids; SFAs = saturated fatty acids; MUFAs = monounsaturated fatty acids; PUFAs = Polyunsaturated fatty acids; EPA = eicosapentaenoic acid; DHA = docosahexaenoic acid; ARA = arachidonic acid; CTRL= control diet; HI5= 5% of HI meal; HI10= 10% of HI; HI15= 15% of HI meal.

4.2.2 Fish, feeding trial, and sampling

The experiment was carried out at the Laboratory of Aquaculture, Department of Veterinary Medical Sciences of the University of Bologna, Cesenatico, Italy. Sea bream specimens were obtained from Panittica Italia (Torre Canne di Fasano, Brindisi, Italy). At the beginning of the trial, 50 fish (initial weight: 98.6±0.6 g) per tank were randomly distributed into 12 450 L square tanks. Experimental diets were assigned randomly and administered by hand to triplicate groups to visual satiation twice a day (h 8.30 and h 16.00) for 6 days a week over 113 days. Tanks were provided with natural seawater and connected to a closed recirculation system (RAS) (overall water volume: 6m³; Oxygen level 8.0±1.0mg/L; Temperature 24±1.0°C, Salinity 25 g/L, artificial photoperiod of 12 h light and 12 h dark.). The oxygen level was kept constant through a liquid oxygen system regulated by a software program (B&G Sinergia snc, Chioggia, Italy). Ammonia (total ammonia nitrogen ≤0.1mg/L) and nitrite (≤0.2mg/L) were daily monitored spectrophotometrically (Spectroquant Nova 60, Merck, Lab business, Darmstadt, Germany). Salinity was measured by a salt refractometer (106 ATC, Giorgio Bormac S.r.l., Carpi, Italy), and sodium bicarbonate was added daily to keep pH at 7.8–8.2. (Pelusio *et al.*, 2021). At the end of the trial a total of 48 sea bream (4 fish/tank) for technological analysis, and a total of 84 fish (7 fish/tank) for sensory analysis, were ice-killed.

4.2.3 Technological analysis

The fish were eviscerated, stored in ice until the complete resolution of *rigor mortis*, and filleted at 48 h *postmortem*. For each sea bream, one fillet was marinated (8% NaCl, 1% CH₃COOH for 48 h at 4 °C) and used for the determination of purge loss, which represents the ability of meat to retain the marinade solution during refrigerated storage. The other fillet was used for the measurement of ultimate pH as described by Jeacocke, 2007, total protein solubility as proposed by Sotelo *et al.* (1994), and oxidative status of both lipid and protein fractions through the determination of thiobarbituric acid reactive substances (i.e., TBARS) and carbonyls content, respectively, following the procedures proposed by Bao and Ertbjerg (2015), and Soglia *et al.* (2016).

4.2.4 Fillets cooking for sensory profile

The specimens of sea bream were filleted manually, keeping the skin as a protection of the fillet both for storage and for subsequent cooking. Each examined diet (Ctrl, HI5, HI10, HI15) was retained and quickly transported to the sensory analysis laboratory where the samples were washed and dried and each sea bream fillet was individually wrapped with aluminium foil to protect them from light and therefore from oxidation. Finally, the processed fillets were placed under vacuum and then frozen within 12 hours of tank capture, at -80 °C until analysis.

The fillets to be analysed on the day were previously thawed by placing them at 3 °C for about 12 hours and keeping them in their packaging. The next morning, tap water was boiled in a stainless-steel pot (Ø 32 cm) by placing it on a Schott Ceran glass-ceramic induction plate. A large stainless-steel sieve was placed on top of the pot and all the fillets were allocated, with the skin facing down, taking care to completely cover them. The fillets' cooking time was standardised based on their weight (100 g each) and set to 4 minutes. After this time, each fillet was delicately removed and placed inside a plastic food box equipped with a cover (750 cc capacity), aligned with the others on the panellist tray.

4.2.5 The sensory panel

The sensory analysis group (Panel) was made up of 10 individuals of both sexes working at the aquaculture centre in Cesenatico, University of Bologna, and operating under the guidance of an experienced panel leader. The sex ratio, Panel leader excluded, was M:F = 5:4 and the age range was 23:58 years. Each panellist attended a 20-hour course aimed at verifying their normosensitivity (ISO 8586: 2012) as well as their proficiency in discriminant tests (mainly triangular tests) (ISO 4120:2021) and descriptive tests (quantitative descriptive analysis, QDA) according to Stone and Sidel (1993).

Because of the Italian government restrictions due to the COVID 19 pandemic, the entire process of creating and training, as well as the triplicate final evaluation, the ballot, and the final evaluation was conducted remotely (Teams platform), with the help of a rather large number of physical references provided each panellist, aimed at anchoring and therefore stabilizing the sensory response as suggested by Rainey (1986).

4.2.6 Set up and performing of sensory analysis

Four hours were spent familiarizing with the main sensory traits of sea bream from different origins. Each sample was named with a random three-digit code. For each sample, the panellists identified 40 traits according to Civille and Lyon (1996) and Hyldig (2012), and then reduced them to 31 according to ISO 11035: 1994. Table 3 shows traits along with the definitions and references, as derived from the panel's work during 6 dedicated sessions. In these sessions, the initial work of naming and defining the descriptors was carried out remotely, each panellist being placed in an odourless room connected to all others via the Teams platform. This led the panel to use a single set of widely agreed traits. Once the final ballot was assembled, the actual samples were prepared as described above, and analysis was performed within the following week to allow panellists to have stabilise and remember all references. Also, natural mineral water 4neutralizers. The panellists were instructed to give priority to the evaluation of the olfactory notes (direct ways) as they are rather labile, to then move on to the examination of the appearance, then to the aroma (retronasal ways), to the basic taste, flavour, and to the mouth feels, to finish with the texture aspects of a mechanical, geometric, and chemical type. Therefore, each panellist tray contained as many permitted plastic boxes as there were experimental theses (including control) plus a dozen references duly kept warm. The panel test was blind according to ISO 11132-2021 .

Table 3. List of descriptors for Quantitative Descriptive Analysis.

Aspect	
Colour	Visual estimate of the level of fullness of the white colour, from off-white to snow-white (Min: off-white; MAX: snow-white) ¹
Coagulated proteins	Visual estimate of the level of presence on the fillet of sarcoplasmic coagulated proteins, as a greyish-white layer (Min: absence; MAX: coverage of the entire surface)
Visual flakiness	The ease with which the fish separates into "layers" (flakes), when stressed (Min: swordfish; MAX: salmon)
Smell	
Overall intensity	The overall strength of the aromatic substances perceived through the direct pathways (orthonasal) when opening the vessel containing the product (Min: 0% reference orange juice; MAX: 100% of the same reference juice)
Briny	Aromatic substances perceived through the direct pathways characteristic of seawater (Min: absence; MAX: intravalve liquid of mussel)
Boiled potato	Aromatic substances perceived through the direct pathways associated with yellow potatoes boiled without skin (Min: absence; MAX: boiled yellow potato)
Steamed fish.	Aromatic substances perceived through the direct pathways associated with steam fish flesh cooked (sea bass or <i>Dicentrarchus labrax</i>) (Min: absence; Max: steamed reared sea bass fillet)
Octopus	Aromatic substances perceived by the direct pathways associated with boiled octopus tentacles (<i>Octopus vulgaris</i>) (Min: absence; Max: boiled octopus tentacle)
Boiled milk	Aromatic substances perceived through the direct pathways associated with fresh whole milk heated up to the boiling point (Min: absence; Max: boiled milk)
Boiled courgette	Aromatic substances perceived through the direct pathways associated with the core of boiled light green courgette (Min: absence; Max: boiled courgette)
Earthy	Aromatic substances perceived through the direct pathways associated with yellow potatoes boiled with skin (Min: absence; Max: boiled yellow potato with skin)
Chicken breast	Aromatic substances perceived through the direct pathways associated with boiled chicken breast (Min: absence; Max: boiled chicken breast)
Basic tastes	
Salty	Taste on the tongue stimulated by sodium salts, in particular sodium chloride (Min: absence; Max: 8.5 ml of stock solution (§) in 500 ml of water)
Sweet	Taste on the tongue stimulated by sugars and highly sweetening substances (Min: absence; Max: 15 ml of stock solution in 500 ml of water)
Acid	Taste on the tongue stimulated by organic acids, such as lactic acid and acetic acid (Min: absence; Max: 20 ml of stock solution in 500 ml of water)
Bitter	Taste on the tongue stimulated by solutions of caffeine, quinine and other alkaloids (Min: absence; Max: 30 ml of stock solution in 500 ml of water)
Umami	Taste on the tongue stimulated by monosodium glutamate (MSG) and some other nucleotides (Min: absence; Max: 4 ml of stock solution in 500 ml of water)

Descriptors and physical references produced for the benefit of panellers

Mouth feeling

Metallic The sensation of a mouth stimulated, for example, by a metal coin, as well as natural canned tuna, canned tomato juice, etc.
(Min: absence; Max: 0.25 g of ferrous sulphate in 250 g of pulp)

Astringent The sensation on the tongue or mucous membranes of the oral cavity described as dry or mouth puckering and associated with tannins or alum (unripe fruits, strong tea)
(Min: absence; Max: 1.5 g of tannic acid in 250 g of pulp)

Aroma

Overall intensity The overall strength of the aromatic substances perceived through the back of the nose when opening the vessel containing the product
(Min: 0% juice; Max: 100% juice)

Chicken breast Aromatic substances perceived by the retronasal passages associated with boiled chicken breast
(Min: absence; Max: boiled chicken breast)

Boiled potato Aromatic substances perceived by the retronasal passages associated with yellow potatoes boiled without skin
(Min: absence; Max: boiled potato)

Steamed salmon Aromatic substances perceived by the retronasal pathways associated with steamed salmon (*Salmo salar*)
(Min: absence; Max: steamed salmon)

Earthy Aromatic substances perceived by the retronasal pathways associated with yellow potatoes boiled with skin
(Min: absence; Max: boiled yellow potato with skin)

Boiled courgette Aromatic substances perceived by the retronasal pathways associated with the core of boiled light green courgette
(Min: absence; Max: boiled courgette)

Octopus Aromatic substances perceived through the retronasal pathways associated with boiled octopus tentacles (*Octopus vulgaris*)
(Min: absence; Max: boiled octopus tentacle)

Texture²

Hardness Mechanical textural attribute that refers to the strength needed to reach a certain deformation of, or penetration into, a product. In the oral cavity it is perceived by compressing a tiny amount of flesh (approx. 12 x 20 mm) between the molars
(Min: halibut; Max: swordfish)

Chewiness Mechanical textural attribute that refers to the cohesiveness of the food and the chewing count needed to prepare the standard bite for swallowing
(Min: halibut; Max: swordfish)

Fibrousness Geometric textural attribute that refers to the perception, in food, of fibers elongated and oriented in the same direction. To appreciate this trait, it is suggested to manipulate with the tongue the standard bite against the hard palate
(Min: halibut; Max: swordfish)

Moisture perception. Surface textural attribute that describes the perception of water absorbed or released by the product. To appreciate it, "work" the standard bite by squeezing it with the tongue against the hard palate.
Min: swordfish; Max: halibut)

Greasiness Surface textural attribute that expresses the perception of the quantity of fat present in a product. Evaluate the lipid film left by the standard bite on the mouth surfaces
(Min: halibut; Max: mackerel)

List of descriptors for appearance, odors, and basic taste developed by a 10-member trained sensory panel for sea bream Quantitative Descriptive Analysis.

(§) Stock solution = "mother" solution of each basic taste, with different concentration depending on the relevant taste.

¹10-cm unstructured line scale was adopted, anchored respectively at 0 and 10.0 cm from the beginning of the scale itself (Stone et al., 1980)

²Attributes referred to a "Standard bite size" (cm 1.5x1.5) natural thickness of the product, up to 1.5 cm.

4.2.7 Nutritional analysis and total lipids and fatty acids composition

Five fish per tank were sacrificed and the dorsal-left skinned fillet was collected for proximate composition analysis. Moisture content was obtained by weight loss after drying samples on a stove at 105 °C overnight. Crude protein was determined as total nitrogen (N) by using the Kjeldahl method and multiplying N by 6.25 Behr (for nitrogen determination: BehrS5 equipment). Total lipids were determined according to Bligh and Dyer's (1959) extraction method (equipment: VELP ser 148 e VELP HU6). Ash content was estimated by incineration to a constant weight in a muffle oven at 550 °C for 3 hours.

Energy values, expressed in Kcal/100g, were derived multiplying the grams of protein and fat by factors 4 and 9 respectively (USDA, 2016).

Fatty acids composition analysis was performed according to ISO16958:2015 and shown in Table 4.

Table 4. List of total fatty acids composition of sea bream fillets fed the control diet and the three diets containing different inclusion levels of *Hermetia illucens* (HI) larvae meal.

<i>FAs (g/100 g)</i>	CTRL	HI5	HI10	HI15	<i>P value</i>
12:0	0.005 ^a ± 0.001	0.005 ^a ± 0.009	0.066 ^b ± 0.014	0.117 ^c ± 0.025	<0.0001
14:0	0.207 ^a ± 0.043	0.297 ^b ± 0.049	0.292 ^b ± 0.049	0.344 ^b ± 0.053	0.005
15:0	0.016 ^a ± 0.003	0.020 ^b ± 0.004	0.020 ^{ab} ± 0.004	0.020 ^b ± 0.004	0.013
16:0	1.273 ± 0.153	1.68 ± 0.200	1.487 ± 0.180	1.607 ± 0.193	0.117
17:0	0.016 ^a ± 0.003	0.020 ^b ± 0.004	0.019 ^{ab} ± 0.004	0.020 ^b ± 0.004	0.021
18:0	0.302 ± 0.050	0.386 ± 0.057	0.345 ± 0.053	0.346 ± 0.053	0.182
20:0	0.021 ^a ± 0.004	0.027 ^b ± 0.006	0.025 ^{ab} ± 0.005	0.025 ^{ab} ± 0.005	0.025
22:0	0.011 ^a ± 0.002	0.015 ^b ± 0.003	0.013 ^{ab} ± 0.003	0.013 ^{ab} ± 0.003	0.048
Total SFAs	1.943 ± 0.167	2.597 ± 0.217	2.363 ± 0.200	2.6 ± 0.213	0.459
16:1 total	0.373 ± 0.079	0.497 ± 0.420	0.457 ± 0.308	0.503 ± 0.307	0.090
17:1 total	0.022 ± 0.004	0.026 ± 0.004	0.024 ± 0.004	0.025 ± 0.004	0.375
18:1 total	3.207 ± 0.300	4.057 ± 0.360	3.593 ± 0.333	3.627 ± 0.333	0.175
20:1 total	0.147 ± 0.031	0.187 ± 0.040	0.174 ± 0.037	0.173 ± 0.036	0.112
22:1 total	0.098 ± 0.015	0.12 ± 0.019	0.108 ± 0.016	0.109 ± 0.016	0.205
Total MUFAs	3.893 ± 0.517	4.947 ± 0.553	4.417 ± 0.537	4.493 ± 0.533	0.165
18:3 total	0.325 ± 0.048	0.394 ± 0.054	0.351 ± 0.050	0.348 ± 0.050	0.102
18:4 n3	0.048 ^a ± 0.010	0.062 ^b ± 0.013	0.056 ^{ab} ± 0.012	0.060 ^{ab} ± 0.013	0.032
20:4 n6 (ARA)	0.036 ^{ab} ± 0.001	0.042 ^b ± 0.001	0.041 ^b ± 0.003	0.034 ^a ± 0.010	0.024
20:5 n3 (EPA)	0.283 ^a ± 0.012	0.372 ^b ± 0.013	0.355 ^{ab} ± 0.032	0.373 ^{ab} ± 0.035	0.021
22:6 n3 (DHA)	0.441 ± 0.012	0.502 ± 0.020	0.476 ± 0.019	0.422 ± 0.020	0.096
EPA+DHA	0.724 ± 0.024	0.874 ± 0.032	0.832 ± 0.050	0.823 ± 0.067	0.061

<i>FAs (g/100 g)</i>	CTRL	HI5	HI10	HI15	<i>P value</i>
PUFAs (> C20)	0.657 ± 0.073	0.774 ± 0.082	0.744 ± 0.079	0.714 ± 0.077	0.067
Total PUFAs	2.527 ± 0.167	3.1 ± 0.197	2.893 ± 0.187	2.89 ± 0.187	0.066
PUFAs / MUFAs	0.649 ± 0.096	0.627 ± 0.081	0.658 ± 0.091	0.649 ± 0.090	0.592
PUFAs / SFAs	1.300 ^{cb} ± 0.143	1.193 ^{ab} ± 0.127	1.230 ^{ab} ± 0.133	1.120 ^a ± 0.123	0.020

FAs = Fatty acids; SFAs = saturated fatty acids; MUFAs = monounsaturated fatty acids; PUFAs = Polyunsaturated fatty acids; EPA = eicosapentaenoic acid; DHA = docosahexaenoic acid; ARA = arachidonic acid; CTRL= control diet; HI5= 5% of HI meal; HI10= 10% of HI; HI15= 15% of HI meal.

4.2.8 Statistical analysis

All data are presented as mean ± standard deviation (SD). The tank was used as the experimental unit for analysing growth performance, and a pool of five sampled fish was considered the experimental unit for analysing carcass composition. Data from sensorial, technological, and nutritional analyses were analysed by a one-way ANOVA. The differences among treatments were considered significant at $P \leq 0.05$, and in this case, Tukey's post hoc test was performed. The data were checked for normality of variance by the Shapiro-Wilk tests. GraphPad Prism was used to conduct the statistical analyses.

4.3 Results and Discussion

4.3.1 Fillet's nutritional characteristics

At the end of the trial, no significant differences in growth and feed utilization were detected between diets (final body weight, g: 271.6-282.3, $P=0.400$; specific growth rate, % body weight /day: 0.89-0.93, $P=0.184$; feed conversion rate: 1.29-1.32, $P=0.492$). Analyses of fatty acid composition (Table 3) showed that some SFAs were significantly higher in fillets of fish-fed diets with HI meal inclusion. Specifically, C14:0 presented higher values ($P=0.005$) for fillets of fish-fed diets containing HI with respect to the CTRL; C15:0 and C17:0 presented higher values (respectively $P=0.00128$; $P=0.0209$) for HI5 and HI15 compared to the control; C20:0 and C22:0 showed a significance (respectively $P=0.0253$; $P=0.0488$) in HI5 which had higher values in regard to the CTRL; C12:0 showed no differences among CTRL and HI5, while HI10 was significantly different concerning CTRL and HI5, and HI15 was higher compared to all the other diets ($P < 0.0001$).

It has been observed that SFAs C12:0 and C14:0 increase in the fillet with the increase of HI inclusion, in fish as well as in other species such as broiler chicks (Ross-308) (Altmann *et al.*, 2020; Borgogno *et al.*, 2017; Caimi *et al.*, 2020b; Dalle Zotte, 2021; Stejskal *et al.*, 2020, Bruni *et al.*, 2020a, 2020b; Mancini *et al.*, 2018; Renna *et al.*, 2017). In this study, only C12:0 increased in fillets with the increase

of HI meal inclusion, and the other statistically significant SFAs showed an increase in all diets containing HI meal compared to CTRL.

In the present study, although not significantly different, the total monounsaturated fatty acids (MUFAs) content was higher in the HI diets than in the control diet. In general, MUFAs showed no significant differences among treatments ($P=0.1648$).

Similar data were presented by Hoc *et al.* (2021), and Moutinho *et al.* (2021). On the contrary, Stejskal *et al.* (2020) stated that MUFAs followed a pattern similar to SFAs, increasing with the increase of HI meal inclusion.

In this study, no significant differences were found among treatments also in polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs) ($P=0.0657$). In particular, the level of docosahexaenoic acid (DHA), eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA), and arachidonic acid (ARA), DHA values did not show significant differences between diets ($P=0.0956$). EPA was higher in the HI5 diet than the CTRL diet ($P=0.0211$), while ARA displayed lower values in HI15 with respect to HI5 and HI10 diets ($P=0.0236$). It is known that the fillet content in FAs reflects that of the diets in teleost species (Parma *et al.*, 2019; Pulido *et al.*, 2022). In this regard, it should be mentioned that insect meal, being made up of terrestrial insects, shows a deficiency in FAs that could result in a lowering of PUFAs content, especially n-3, in the fillet. This aspect is one of the main inconveniences of using insect meal, and indeed several studies reported that the PUFAs content decreased with the increase of HI inclusion (Altmann *et al.*, 2020; Borgogno *et al.*, 2017; Carvalho *et al.*, 2023; Lock *et al.*, 2016; Mancini *et al.*, 2018; Oteri *et al.*, 2022; Pulido *et al.*, 2022; Renna *et al.*, 2017; Secci *et al.*, 2019; Stejskal *et al.*, 2020; St-Hilaire *et al.*, 2007; Zarantoniello *et al.*, 2022). However, in the present study the quantities of PUFAs did not decrease and quite reflect those of the diets. This is due to the practical low fish meal level employed in the CTRL diet. Thus, the partial substitution of FM with HI did not give an overall effect on diet FAs composition. Data from this study seem to meet the results of previous assessments that tested HI in substitution of FM with a control diet rich in plant ingredients. Indeed, no significant difference in PUFAs n-3 was observed in trout (Bruni *et al.*, 2020b), a slight increase in PUFAs n-3 was observed in salmon (Bruni *et al.*, 2020a), and in pikeperch, DHA decreased with the increasing HI meal inclusion, while n-6 FAs showed the opposite trend, and no significant differences were found in total PUFAs among treatments (Stejskal *et al.*, 2023).

In addition, the fish fillets tested in this study show an excellent EPA+DHA content. According to EFSA Scientific Committee (2015), every adult should take 250 mg of EPA+DHA per day, about 1750 mg per week, consuming two portions of fish of 150 g each. Two portions of fillet from all four diets tested in this study exceed the weekly EPA+DHA requirement, in particular, HI diets which contain on average 119 mg/100 g more EPA+DHA compared to the control diet.

Data regarding the fillet's proximate composition are shown in Table 5. According to the results, no significant differences were found in moisture, crude protein, crude fat, ash, and energy values among treatments ($P>0.05$).

Table 5. Proximate composition of sea bream's (*Sparus aurata*) fillets fed the control diet and the three diets containing different inclusion levels of *Hermetia illucens* (HI) larvae meal.

<i>Proximate composition (%)</i>	<i>Experimental diets</i>				<i>P</i> value
	CTRL	HI5	HI10	HI15	
Moisture	68.0±0.68	66.7±0.89	67.6±0.55	66.5±1.33	0.224
Crude protein	21.5±0.61	20.9±0.06	21.0±0.18	20.8±0.10	0.113
Ash	1.55±0.04	1.51±0.04	1.52±0.13	1.49±0.07	0.851
Crude fat	7.38±1.35	8.68±1.92	8.64±1.02	9.92±3.15	0.539
Energy (Kcal/100g)	100.0±2.83	97.1±0.23	97.6±1.78	96.7±0.83	0.173

Data are given as the mean (n=3). CTRL= control diet; HI5= 5% of HI meal; HI10= 10% of HI; HI15= 15% of HI meal.

4.3.2 Technological Analysis

Data concerning fillets' main technological properties and oxidative status are shown in Table 6. Overall data showed that the replacement of conventional protein sources with HI larvae meal up to a level of 15% did not affect the main technological properties and the oxidative status of sea bream fillets. This outcome is corroborated by several recent studies aimed at evaluating the effects of the inclusion of HI larvae meal on technological properties not only of gilthead sea bream (Pulido-Rodríguez *et al.*, 2021) but also for other fish species, such as rainbow trout (Renna *et al.*, 2017).

It is worth mentioning that the inclusion of HI larvae meal did not affect the ultimate pH of fish fillets, thus suggesting that the pattern of *post-mortem* acidification was not influenced by the dietary treatment. This result confirms what was previously found in research carried out by Renna *et al.* (2017), in which the muscular pH of rainbow trout fed with HI larvae meal up to 50% was not significantly modified. That is particularly relevant when considering the relationship between muscular pH and the technological properties of fish muscles, such as their ability to retain water (Liu *et al.*, 2010). This outcome is further corroborated by the results concerning purge loss and protein solubility obtained within this study (respectively, $P=0.706$; $P=0.302$). As for the oxidative status of fish muscles, the absence of significant differences in TBARS content ($P=0.554$) suggests that the inclusion of HI larvae meal, regardless of its level, did not result in higher oxidation of the lipid fraction. As for protein oxidation, carbonyl levels tended to be higher in the HI5 group ($P=0.078$). However, it should be noted that this difference is of a minor extent, and thus not relevant for the final quality of sea bream fillets.

Table 6. Technological properties and oxidative status of sea bream's (*Sparus aurata*) fillets fed the control diet and the three diets containing different inclusion levels of *Hermetia illucens* (HI) larvae meal.

<i>Experimental diets</i>					
<i>Technological properties</i>	CTRL	HI5	HI10	HI15	<i>P</i> value
pH	6.26 ± 0.06	6.27 ± 0.08	6.26 ± 0.08	6.24 ± 0.05	0.796
Purge loss (%)	1.75 ± 0.51	1.47 ± 0.56	1.58 ± 0.43	1.54 ± 0.38	0.706
Protein solubility (mg/g)	139.2 ± 21.0	125.1 ± 30.9	142.7 ± 22.4	137.6 ± 26.8	0.302
<i>Oxidative status</i>					
¹ TBARS (mg MDA/kg)	0.64 ± 0.04	0.66 ± 0.02	0.64 ± 0.06	0.66 ± 0.04	0.554
Carbonyls (nmol/mg)	1.77 ± 0.70	2.39 ± 0.65	1.98 ± 0.43	1.85 ± 0.33	0.078

Data are given as the mean (n=12). ¹TBARS= thiobarbituric acid reactive substances. CTRL= control diet; HI5= 5% of HI meal; HI10= 10% of HI; HI15= 15% of HI meal.

4.3.3 Sensory Analysis

Figure 1. Complete sensory profile of sea bream from a feeding which control diet was compared with different percentages of insect diets. From right to left: O = odour, A= aspect, T = texture, F = flavour, Bt = based tastes, Mf = mouth feeling

At the end of the trial, no significant differences ($P>0.05$) were detected in final body weights among treatments (CTRL 273.9±7.86; HI5 282.3±5.12; HI10 271.6±8.69; HI15 273.3±9.14).

Results of different inclusion levels of HI larvae meal (0% CTRL, 5% HI5, 10% HI10, and 15% HI15) in place of FM, based on the list of sensory attributes developed for sea bream are shown in Figure 1.

Most of the attributes considered were not significantly affected ($P \leq 0.05$) by the inclusion of HI. The same result has been encountered also in previous studies on several fish species where HI was included in the substitution of FM (Belghit *et al.*, 2019; Borgogno *et al.*, 2017; Lock *et al.*, 2016; Sealey *et al.*, 2011).

In the present study, a significant result was found regarding the odour ($P=0.0124$) and flavour ($P=0.0329$) trait ‘cooked chicken breast’ between HI5 and HI10 (Figures 2 and 3 respectively).

Figure 2. a. Spider web for Odour scope. From left to right: General intensity, briny, boiled potato, steamed fish, octopus, boiled milk, boiled courgette, earthy, chicken breast; **b.** Statistical differences ($P=0.0124$) in Chicken breast odor descriptor among treatments.

Figure 3. a. Spider web for Flavour scope. From left to right: General intensity, chicken breast, boiled potato, salmon, earthy, boiled courgette, octopus; **b.** Statistical differences ($P=0.0329$) in Chicken breast flavor descriptor among treatments.

4.4 Conclusion

In conclusion, the HI larvae meal dietary inclusion up to 15% does not provoke a difference in the sensory evaluation of the fillet for most of the traits examined.

Also, HI inclusion shows similar technological fish quality compared to the control diet, not compromising the fillet's technological characteristics and oxidative state. Analyses conducted on fillets' fatty acids content showed that SFAs were, in most cases, significantly higher in fillets fed the HI15 diet, confirming that a greater HI meal inclusion leads to higher SFAs content. Moreover, in this study, the inclusion of HI meal did not impair EPA and DHA content. The absence of a significant difference ($P>0.05$) in most of the attributes examined provides further evidence to consumers that feeding sea bream

with diets containing HI meal does not negatively impact fillets' taste and quality.

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Ethical statement

The experiment was designed according to the guidelines of the current European Directive (2010/63/EU) on the protection of animals used for scientific purposes. The experimental protocol was approved by the Ethical Committee of the University of Bologna (Italy) (protocol N° 237050).

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CHAPTER

5.

CONSUMER EXPECTATION AND PERCEPTION OF AQUACULTURE PRODUCTS FEED WITH INSECT MEAL (*TENEBRIO MOLITOR*)

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Abstract

In recent years, insect meal has attracted increasing interest as an innovative protein source to replace fish meal in feed formulations due to its valuable nutritional profile. This re-search aimed to compare the effects of different levels of dietary inclusion (30, 60 and 100 %) of *Tenebrio molitor* larvae meal on the sensory quality of trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) fillets and retrospectively on the acceptability of this protein source to consumers. The results showed that the inclusion of *Tenebrio molitor* larvae meal did not induce sensory changes in the trout fillets, while regarding consumer acceptability and willingness to buy and pay, it was shown how neophobia towards this alternative protein still exists. The work described in this scientific manuscript is relevant because it adds knowledge on the study of consumer acceptability of this protein source.

Keywords: insect meal, *Tenebrio molitor*, sensory profile, consumer expectation, consumer acceptance, Rainbow trout, *Oncorhynchus mykiss*, willingness to buy, willingness to pay.

5.1 Introduction

According to the latest data published by the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), world aquaculture production in 2020 was 122.5 million tonnes, an increase of 3% compared to the previous year and with an estimated average annual growth rate of around 3.3%, due to the growing global demand for healthy and nutritious fish and fish products as a result of the growing world population and changes in eating habits (consumption patterns)[1]. The expected increase in consumption of fish products therefore suggests a necessary adoption of new and more sustainable aqua-culture production systems.

However, there are several obstacles to this rapid expansion of aquaculture, including the application of more restrictive environmental regulations, the decrease in available water and climate change (FAO, 2022). It is precisely the latter that have a very direct impact on aquaculture (Galappaththi et al., 2020), and although these changes vary between geographical areas, the Mediterranean region is expected to be affected faster and more acutely in some respects than other areas (Benito J. et al., 2010). These aspects, such as increasing temperature, changing salinity, decreasing pH, rising sea levels, and changes in ocean productivity, may directly or indirectly impact fisheries and aquaculture (General Fisheries commission for the Mediterranean scientific advisory committee 2009).

The link between these two activities is still highly correlated today, because it is through the capture of wild fish resources that fishmeal and fish oil can be produced that can be used in the production of feed for aquaculture (Malcorps W. 2019). From 2000 onwards, fishmeal (FM), for feed production, became a product of limited availability precisely due to the rapid expansion of the aquaculture sector and the consequent demand for this product outstripping supply (Naylor et al. 2021).

The need, particularly for carnivorous species, for protein in the diet is rather high in both quality and quantity. For this reason, FM has until now been considered the best protein source for feed formulation (Kok et al. 2020). Since a few years ago, the scarcity of this raw material has forced us to explore new alternative and sustainable protein sources (Gasco et al. 2020).

Over the last decade, different alternative, plant (Albrektsen, Mundheim, and Aksnes 2006; De Francesco et al. n.d.) and non-plant sources of protein have been tested, and the growing demand for these new sources of protein and nutrients has led to the observation that, in many parts of the world, insects are already used as food for human and animal consumption. This has prompted scientists to investigate the nutritional properties of this alternative source.

Tenebrio molitor flour is used in this study. This has a high protein value (50% for fat flour up to 82% for non-fat flour) compared to the protein content of good quality FM which can be as high as 73% and soya flour which can contain up to 50% protein (Barroso et al. 2014). Insect flours, and in particular *Tenebrio molitor*, are very rich in essential amino acids, which makes them of high nutritional value. In addition, high levels of minerals such as iron, magnesium, zinc and selenium and low amounts, compared to FM, of calcium and potassium were observed. Vitamins are also contained in a good percentage (Henry et al. 2015). The lipid content within *Tenebrio molitor* can be up to 30%, in contrast to the content found in FM (8.2%) and soybean meal (3%) (Barroso et al. 2014).

The fat content of insects varies between 10 and 70% on a dry matter (Bukkens 1997; Finke 2013; Yang, Siriamornpun, and Li 2006).

Fat is composed of fatty acids. These fatty acids are divided into saturated, monounsaturated and polyunsaturated fatty acids according to their degree of saturation.

The fatty acid composition of insects depends on species and life stage, as well as environmental factors such as diet, temperature and light (Finke M.D. and Oonincx D.G.A.B. 2017).

Commercially produced insects appear to have a higher fat content than those collected in the wild (Finke 2002). This could be due to lower energy expenditure in captivity, access to high-energy diets, or both.

In general, naturally caught insects contain relatively high amounts of linoleic acid (18:2 n-6) and linolenic acid (18:3 n-3).

Commercially bred insects also contain high levels of linoleic acid, but much lower levels of linolenic acid much lower than in wild insects, because their diet often contains large amounts of cereals and cereal products, which have low levels of linolenic acid (Oonincx and Finke 2021).

In addition, *Tenebrio molitor* fats are also rich in polyunsaturated fatty acids (ω 6) such as linolenic acid, which is also normally found in plant products, while arachidonic acid (ARA), which is found in animal products, is only present in traces. Polyunsaturated fatty acids are involved in the production of the lipid component of all cell membranes, both animal and human (Ravzanaadii et al. 2012).

Nutritional analyses on the meal derived from this insect type meant that it could be used and evaluated as an ingredient in diets for livestock (Pietras et al. 2021) and for feeding in aqua-culture species. Several studies showed that it is possible to replace FM with *Tenebrio molitor* meal at doses of no more than 50%; in fact, above this percentage, a reduction in growth rate and fattening was noted (Fabrikov et al. 2021; Gasco et al. 2019, 2020; Iaconisi et al. 2019; Melenchón et al. 2021; Rema et al. 2019).

These studies corroborated to show that *Tenebrio Molitor* meal is a viable alternative to the use of fish ingredients in animal feed.

Given the growing interest in insect products as an alternative source of protein, the acceptability and knowledge of consumer preferences for insect foods may be critical. This knowledge would enable informed decisions on the production of these foods, particularly for Western countries where insect food consumption is largely non-existent (Giotis and Drichoutis 2021a). These studies are, to date, scarce (Sogari, Menozzi, and Mora 2019a) however, we know that humans generally avoid unfamiliar foods because they suffer from neophobia (Martins and Pliner 2005).

Although we acknowledge the contribution of such studies, we agree with other authors who argue that insects could be more easily introduced into consumers' daily diets by developing products that involve eating insects directly but insect-based feed (Kim et al. 2019; Tan, Verbaan, and Stieger 2017).

This was also demonstrated by Verbeke et al. (Verbeke et al. 2015) who in a research conducted in Belgium, studied consumer acceptance of the use of insects in feed and the results showed that it was widely accepted and that the respondents were more willing to accept insects as animal feed than the direct consumption of insects in their diet because they are not familiar with insects as part of the human diet.

La Barbera et al. (La Barbera et al. 2020) in research conducted to understand the main drivers and barriers related to Western consumers' acceptance of foods with insect-derived ingredients found that acceptance of indirect entomophagy does not necessarily indicate acceptance of direct entomophagy

and in fact may make insect food appear 'good for animals, bad for humans' (De Faria Domingues et al. 2020).

To date, studies on the profile of consumers who are more likely to buy insect products, such as the one conducted by Baldi et al. (Baldi et al. 2022) and Sogari et al. (Sogari, Amato, et al. 2019) point out that younger consumers, regardless of gender, occupation or education, but with a slightly higher income, trust innovation in food production and are active in the search for new food sources.

This study is a step towards an even greater understanding of consumer acceptance of new products, such as fish raised on insects-based feed.

5.2 Materials and Methods

5.2.1 Ethical approval

The study was approved by the Ethics Committee of the Institute of Agri-Food Research and Technology (IRTA), registration number CCSC 31/2023, in accordance with legal requirements related to ethical principles of research with human participants (Declaration of Helsinki 1 and Belmont Report). Each participant provided written informed consent to take part in the study.

5.2.2 Fish Sample

Trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) fed with feed containing different percentages of insect meal instead of fish meal, control (CRL), 30, 60, 100% insect meal, were reared at IRTA in San Carlos de la Rápita (Table 1). At the end of the fattening phase, they were filleted and packed in plastic bags and frozen. The fillets were then transported to the IRTA in Monells where they were again vacuum-packed in aluminium food bags to prevent oxidation and placed again in a cell at -18°.

Table 1. Ingredients and proximate composition of the four experimental diets provided to rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*). Three diets contained different inclusion levels of *Tenebrio molitor* meal in substitution of fish meal (FM).

<i>Experimental diets</i>				
<i>Ingredients (%)</i>	CTRL	30%	60%	100%
Fishmeal 60	12,0	8,4	4,8	0,0
Poultry meal	8,0	8,0	8,0	8,0
Porcine blood meal	6,0	6,0	6,0	6,0
Feathermeal hydrolysate	8,0	8,0	8,0	8,0
Insect meal - MEALFOOD	0,0	3,6	7,2	12,0
Soy protein concentrate	6,0	4,8	3,6	1,8
Corn gluten meal	8,0	8,0	8,0	8,0
Soybean meal	10,0	10,0	10,0	10,0
Sunflower meal 40	2,25	2,25	2,25	2,25
Wheat meal	7,0	7,65	8,55	9,62
Pea starch	4,8	4,8	4,8	4,8
Vitamin and mineral premix	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0
Antioxidant	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,2
MAP (Monoammonium phosphate)	2,2	2,5	2,7	3,1
L-Lysine HCl 99%	0,5	0,6	0,65	0,8
L-Tryptophan			0,02	0,05
DL-Methionine	0,05	0,1	0,13	0,18
Fish oil	8,0	8,0	8,0	8,0
Rapeseed oil	16,0	16,1	16,1	16,2
<i>Proximate Composition</i>				
Crude protein%	42,0	42,0	42,0	42,0
Crude fat%	25,0	25,0	25,0	25,0
Ash%	7,4	7,0	6,5	6,0
Fiber%	1,7	1,6	1,5	1,3
Gross energy, MJ/kg	22,6	22,6	22,7	22,7

CTRL= control diet; 30%= 30% of TM meal; 60%= 60% of TM meal; 100%= 100% of TM meal.

5.2.3 Sensory analysis

This study was carried out by a sensory panel of 7 individuals, all of whom had previous experience in sensory analysis of different types of products. The panelists were asked to identify and generate sensory attributes to characterise and differentiate products fed these experimental diets. Two sessions were spent familiarising themselves with and selecting the descriptors.

The 23 descriptors shown in Table 2 were chosen by means of the Check-All-That-Apply (CATA) method from a list of 58 attributes obtained from a literature work (Belghit et al. 2019a; Borgogno et al. 2017a; Lazo, Claret, and Guerrero 2016; Lock, Arsiwalla, and Waagbø 2016; Pereira et al. 2022). To confirm the discriminating ability of the selected descriptors, the evaluators then quantified the selected attributes in another session. All chosen descriptors proved to be discriminating for the products under investigation.

Table 2. Selected descriptors used for the final descriptive profile along with their de-scription.

Attributes	Description
ODOUR	
Odour intensity	Intensity of odour
Earthy	Intensity of odour like humid earth
Fish oil	Intensity of characteristic odour
Biscuit/Vanilla	Intensity of odour like biscuits
Boiled potato /Vegetables	Intensity of odour like cooked vegetables
APPARENCE	
Exudate quantity	Quantity of liquid released after cooking the sample
Fat droplets	Fat released in fish exudate in the form of oil droplets
Colour intensity of exudate	Yellow colour intensity of the exudate
Turbidity exudate	Suspended particles in exudate that block trasparency
Colour intensity	Colour intensity from white to light brown inside the flesh of the fish
FLAVOUR	
Flavour intensity	Intensity of flavour
Earthy	Intensity of flavour like humid earth
Fish oil	Intensity of characteristic flavour
Acid	Intensity of flavour like citric acid
Sweet	Intensity of flavour like sugar
Bitter	Intensity of flavour like caffeine

Attributes	Description
Persistence/Aftertaste	Duration of stimulus in the oral cavity after swallowing
TEXTURE¹	
Firmness	Force required to deform the fillet between the tongue and palate
Teeth adherence	Degree in which fish sticks between molars
Chewiness	Number of chews before swallowing
Grasiness	Surface attribute that expresses the perception of the quantity of fat present in a product.
Pastiness	Degree in which fish turns in to a paste after chewing
Flakiness	Degree of fish disintegration in the first bite

List of descriptors for appearance, odors, and basic taste developed by a 10-member trained sensory panel for sea bream Quantitative Descriptive Analysis. ¹Attributes referred to a “Standard bite size” (cm 1.5x1.5) natural thickness of the product, up to 1.5 cm.

Once the final list of descriptors was defined, in order to facilitate the training of pan-elists (International Organization for Standardization 1994), reference scales were used using those proposed by Lazo et al. (Lazo et al. 2017) to identify high and low quantities for each selected sensory descriptor. Once the final form was assembled, the samples were evaluated quantitatively in three different sessions using the Quantitative descriptive analysis method (Kemp S. E. 2018; Stone H. 1993).

Samples that had been stored for 5 months in cold storage at -18° were thawed the evening before the analysis by placing them in the refrigerator at 4°. The following morning the fillets were cut into 2 pieces from each fillet, using only the dorsal side, and placed in individual transparent glass jars (model B-250, Juvasa, Spain) to make the sample viewable for appearance analysis.

The samples were then baked in a conventional oven at a temperature of 115° for 14 minutes. The lids of the jars were used throughout the preparation and baking until the final evaluation to preserve the smell of the samples. Immediately after cooking, the jars were placed inside a portable electric heater (Solac, model 212, 220-240 V) to keep them warm until tasting. In each session, the order in which the samples were presented and the first order and carry over effects were eliminated using a special experimental de-sign (Macfie, Bratchell, and Greenhoff 1989).

The sensory evaluation was performed in a tasting room designed according to ISO guidelines (International Organization for Standardization 2007). Each panelist evaluated the samples placed inside the portable electric heating chamber, to maintain the temperature, in a set order. The samples were evaluated using a semi-structured 10 cm-linear scale anchored at both ends, 0 for no descriptor, 10 for maximum intensity. All panelists used water, to be drunk between samples, as a palate neutraliser.

5.2.4 Consumer acceptance

5.2.4.a Participants

A total of 116 consumers were recruited between the cities of Barcelona and Madrid through the marketing agency Silliker S.A.U. (Mérieux NutriSciences) using a re-cruitment questionnaire specifically created for this study. Participants had to be consumers of the species under study, be between 18-70 years of age and comprise 50% women and 50% men, be willing to sample trout fillets fed with feed that included meal of animal origin (crustacean, insect, egg protein) instead of fish meal.

5.2.4.b Questionnaire

To assess consumers' expectations and behaviour towards insect-fed animal products, we designed and distributed a questionnaire divided into 7 parts in which blind and informed tasting, expectation, perception and willingness to buy and pay for the product were assessed.

Consumers tasted the samples and filled in the questionnaire in the 24-cabin laboratory of the Silliker S.A.U. (Mérieux NutriSciences) consulting centre, located in Barcelona and Madrid. The same company took care of their recruitment and it all took place in one day, per city, in sessions with 20 people at a time.

At the beginning of each session a short presentation of the project was made and explained how the work would be organised to follow.

After signing the informed consent, they were presented with the first part of the questionnaire, which consisted of scoring the liking of the product blindly, followed by tasting. Enjoyment was scored using a 9-point hedonic scale (1= "tasted very much to me", 9= "disgusted very much to me") (Peryam D. R. 1957).

The second part of the questionnaire asked about their expectation, i.e., how much they thought they would like the insect meal-fed product, again using a 9-point liking/disliking scale (1=expect to "dislike extremely", 9=expect to "like extremely") (Cardello A. V. 1994). The same question was also proposed to consumers for the use of crustacean meal and egg protein in order to compare consumer acceptance of more familiar alternative proteins to insect meal, and so that they would not know until then that our focus was on the use of insects.

The third part of the questionnaire again involved scoring the liking of the product, this time the tasting was informed and the consumer knew what percentage of insect meal had been fed into the product they tasted or whether it was the control sample, this was to compare the neophobia of the

use of this meal even when used as feed (Martins and Pliner 2005). The evaluation of liking was carried out in the same way as for the blind sample.

The fourth part involved measuring consumers' perceptions of trout fed with insect meal. The scale used consisted of 7 items, but the questions asked were divided into two sections (Hartmann et al. 2018; Hartmann and Siegrist 2016; Laureati et al. n.d.; Mancuso, Baldi, and Gasco 2016; Sogari, Menozzi, and Mora 2019b).

One of these was asked immediately after the informed tasting of the products using the positive and negative term of the parameter to be scored as the extremes of the scale. The questions asked were: Known-Unfamiliar, Innovative-Common, Safe-Unsafe, Healthy-Unhealthy, Expensive-Expensive, Bad Taste-Good Taste, Low Quality-High Quality, Sustainable-Non-Sustainable, Artificial-Natural, Environmentally Harm-ful-Environmentally Respectful.

The other section was asked at a later stage when the whole tasting part was finished. In this part, the scale available for scoring had as extremes 1= totally disagree, 7= totally agree and was asked whether trout fed with insect meal would be nutritious, would be healthy, would taste good, would be expensive, would be difficult to digest, were produced in an environmentally friendly way, would be of high quality, would be safe for health, would be more sustainable.

The fifth part was focused on assessing the willingness to buy this insect meal product considering that it has a normal price. The scale used was 11-point scale, as the minimum value had 'there is no or almost no chance that I would buy it (1% chance) and as the maximum ' it is certain or practically certain that I will buy it (99% chance) (Piha et al. 2018; Tan et al. 2017).

The sixth part asked how much they would be willing to pay for this product. The scale had as a mean value 0% which means that they would be willing to pay the same as they currently pay, negative percentages that they would pay less and positive percentages that they would be willing to pay more for this product (Giotis and Drichoutis 2021b; Lombardi et al. 2019).

The last, and seventh, part collects socio-demographic information such as gender, age, education, economic situation, frequency of trout consumption and how much they were responsible for buying the groceries at home.

5.2.4.c Statistical analysis

The descriptive data concerning differences between dietary treatments were tested by a three-way ANOVA with a significance level of 95% ($p \leq 0.05$), including dietary treatments and assessors as fixed factors and testing session as a random factor. Tukey's post hoc significant difference test was applied for comparing the mean values of the different treatments.

For the statistical analysis of the consumer analysis, a two-way ANOVA was used in which the consumer was placed as the random factor and the dietary treatments and cities as the fixed factor. This was followed by a Tukey's post hoc significant difference test for comparing the mean values of the different treatments.

The data were analysed using the XLSTAT statistical software, Version 19.6 (2020) (Addinsoft, France).

5.3 Results and Discussion

5.3.1 Sensory analysis

Changes in fish feed ingredients can affect the appearance, smell and aroma of fish fillet (Turchini, Torstensen, and Ng 2009). This could in turn affect the perceived quality of the fillet and consequently consumer acceptance (Belghit et al. 2019b). Indeed, Borgogno et al. (Borgogno et al. 2017b), measuring sensory attributes and physico-chemical parameters, found differences in the perceived intensity of odour, flavour and texture in rainbow trout fillets fed a diet that included insect meal.

In contrast, the statistical analysis performed in this study on the intensity data of sensory attributes to estimate the sample effect (CRL, 30, 60, 100%) found no differences ($P \geq 0.05$) as in Iaconisi et al. (Iaconisi et al. 2017)(Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Spider web diagram of trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) fillets fed four different diets (CRL, 30, 60, 100%). Bt = based tastes, Mf = mouth feeling

However, a 100% substitution of FM with *Tenebrio molitor* resulted in a higher score for the odour Biscuit/Vanilla and Boiled Potato/Vegetables compared to the control group. There were no significant flavour differences between the diet groups, but the numerical scores for earthy, sour, bitter and for flavour intensity and persistence increased with the maximum level of inclusion of *Tenebrio molitor* flour (Borgogno et al. 2017a). Regarding texture, the values with the highest scores coinciding with the highest value of *Tenebrio molitor* inclusion were the Greasiness and Flakiness.

5.3.2 Consumer acceptance and perception

In the face of increasing global threats to food security, public health, and environmental sustainability, insects are considered a new source of human food and animal feed in Western countries (Van Huis 2013; Oonincx and de Boer 2012).

However, despite the advantages of insects as a sustainable and healthy alternative to conventional protein sources, they are generally not considered a viable food source by Western consumers (Giotis and Drichoutis 2021a).

The results show that consumers are more willing to accept products that fit into their traditional diet and that the acceptance of insects as human food also depends greatly on the composition and level of feed processing (Onwezen et al. 2019).

In order to assess consumers' expectation of products fed with insect meal, in this study we asked the question: how much do you think you might like the product fed with insect meal in comparison with the same question referring to the use of crustacean meal and egg meal, two products therefore, which are part of the traditional diet of Western countries. As noted by Tan et al. (Tan et al. 2017), the presence of an invisible insect does not necessarily improve the overall liking for the whole insect product. In fact, our results are in line with what Tan et al (Tan et al. 2017). and Onwezen et al. (Onwezen et al. 2019) said, the expectation towards insect meal was punctuated with a lower value compared to crustacean and egg protein. (Fig. 2)

Figure 2. Histogram diagram of consumer expectation of insect meal in comparison with crustacean meal and egg protein. Statistically significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) between the mean values

Furthermore, when there is no real experience or regular consumption of a food, consumer expectations tend to be based on visual appearance and expected taste. Rozin and Fallon (Rozin et al. 1987) showed that considering insects as food can evoke disgust and the thought of consumption can lead to the expectation and perception of bad taste. Our results on product perception show a statistically significant result when correlated with the Unknow term, where the CRL product, compared to the 100% insect meal product, has a lower score as might be expected. (Table 3)

Table 3. Mean value of perception terms. Different letters in the same row indicate statistically significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) between the mean values.

	Unknown	Unsafe	Healthy	Cheap	Good taste	High quality	Unsustainable	Natural	Environmentally friendly
CRL	2,845b	2,422a	5,793a	4,026a	5,431a	5,026a	3,293a	5,207a	5,009b
30	4,928a	2,897b	5,448b	4,078a	5,103ab	4,845a	3,026a	4,853ab	5,267ab
60	4,879a	2,698b	5,401b	4,121a	4,984b	4,836a	3,083a	4,948b	5,397a
100	5,224a	2,828b	5,241b	4,207a	4,914b	4,828a	2,966a	4,991b	5,388a
P value	<0,0001	0,002	<0,0001	0,456	0,002	0,269	0,222	0,069	0,004

Different letters in the same row indicate statistically significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) between the mean values.

Figure 3. Semantic chart of consumer perception of insect meal. Statistically significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) between the mean values

Another statistically significant result is found in correlation with the Healthy term where, in contrast to Unknown, the still positive score ($>$ of 5) presents the highest value for the CRL product and the lowest for the 100% product. This shows how insect meal is still perceived by consumers as a product that is unsafe for human health because it carries possible diseases and allergies. Given the highly

positive nutritional values of insect meal, one way to increase consumer acceptance may be to use health labels, also suggesting positive attributes (Altmann et al. 2022). Furthermore, according to Sogari et al. (Sogari, Menozzi, and Mora 2019c) it also has a positive impact on animal health by increasing digestive performance.

As mentioned above, Rozin and Fallon (Rozin et al. 1987), demonstrated that considering insects as food can evoke disgust. In fact, their statistically significant result for the Good taste term shows a higher score for the CRL product that gradually decreases as the amount of insect meal increases. However, this is in contrast to the sensory data we presented, which show no statistically significant differences at the (Fig.1) sensory analysis, not for the question asking whether they perceived it as a product with a good taste (4.864). Regarding the Environmentally friendly term, the results, rightly expected, show a statistically significant lower value for the CRL product due to the use of fishmeal, compared to the 100% product. These data are in line with those shown by Benito et al. (Benito and Alonso 2010) in which it is predicted that the Mediterranean region may experience, in some respects, faster and more acute climatic changes than other areas and thus impact directly or indirectly on fisheries and aquaculture with an ever decreasing availability of fishmeal to be used as a feed ingredient.

As shown by the results obtained the product fed with insect meal is perceived by consumers as not being of High quality (4.683) contrary to what Sogari et al. (Sogari, Menozzi, and Mora 2019d) says. However, the insect meal-fed product is perceived by consumers positively when correlated with the terms Nutritious (5.611), Natural (5.5.91), Sustainable (5.5419) as can be seen in Table 4.

Table 4. Overall perceptions of products fed with insect meal.

Overall perception	Medium score
Percep. Nutritious	5,611
Percep. Healty	5,341
Percep. Good taste	4,864
Percep. Natural	5,091
Percep. Expensive	4,282
Percep. Difficulty digesting	4,028
Percep. Envirom. responsible	5,359
Percep. High quality	4,683
Percep. Health insurance	5,241
Percep. Sustainable	5,541

Statistically significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$)

Wanting to assess how information influences the acceptability of the product, we administered, first blindly and then in an informed version, the product to consumers who had to score their liking on a hedonistic 9-point scale (1= "tasted me very much", 9= "disgusted me very much") (Peryam D. R. 1957).

As far as the results of the informed taste test are concerned, we can see that the liking decreases as the increase of insect meal within the product increases, although these data did not show significance, whereas, the blind taste test score shows that there is no significance among the four (CRL, 30, 60, 100%) samples tested (Table 5).

Table 5. Table of mean value of blind and informed tasting.

	Blind	Informed
Crl	6,871 a	6,871a
30	6,836 a	6,603a
60	6,750 a	6,509a
100	6,862 a	6,681a
P value	0,856	0,099

Different letters in the same row indicate statistically significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$)

The commercial potential of unprocessed and processed insect products will depend heavily on the opinion on the sensory liking attribute both before and after tasting (Sogari, Menozzi, and Mora 2018). This is also thanks to the latest technologies in the field of feed that are a valuable aid in the potential to alleviate disgust and even reduce the impact of neophobia, even if affective-emotional reactions are only partially modified by awareness and information (La Barbera et al. 2020).

Regarding the willingness to buy, as could be expected, the results show the CRL product with the highest value (7.345) and gradually this value decreases as the inclusion of insect meal increases (Table 5). This figure shows how strong the neophobia towards this foodstuff still is, despite the fact that the question was asked after the informed tasting.

Regarding the willingness to pay for these products, our results show that the consumer is willing to pay a higher price for the CRL product and a lower price as the insect meal substitution increases. This is not in line with Deely et al. (Deely et al. 2022), according to which consumers are willing to pay more for environmentally friendly food products.

Furthermore, it was noted that the willingness to pay more for such a product is positively correlated with the economic situation of the consumer. (Table 6)

Table 6. Table of willingness to buy and willingness to pay.

	Willingness to buy	Willingness to pay
Ctrl	7,345 a	6,774 a
30	6,578 b	6,289 b
60	6,491 b	6,183 b
100	6,328 b	6,070 b
P value	<0,0001	0,001

Different letters in the same row indicate statistically significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$)

5.4 Conclusions

This study contributes to the scientific literature by examining consumer attitudes and acceptance of an innovative product, insect-fed fish. The focus of the work is also of great interest in the context of the 'circular economy', which sees insect-fed fish as a possible future reality.

Furthermore, considering that a limitation of this study is the specific national/cultural context (Spanish consumers), future experiments will have to make a cross-cultural comparison. Future research should also consider other consumption contexts (restaurant or home consumption) and the stage of preparation (raw or ready-to-eat).

Further studies are also needed to better identify different consumer groups.

Practitioners should therefore try to publicise not only the potential benefits of entomophagy, but also consider taste education as an important tool to change attitudes and negative expectations towards edible insects (Sogari et al. 2018).

The positive experience of tasting products with both visible and processed insects may cause consumers to reconsider their initial negative expectations and attitudes towards entomophagy, encouraging others to eat these novel foods as well.

Furthermore, it appears that indirect approval from others (e.g. family and friends) may be one of the most important factors in the introduction and spread of entomophagy (Sogari 2015; Sogari, Menozzi, and Mora 2017).

5.5 References

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CHAPTER

6.

SETTING UP A NON-DESTRUCTIVE AND CHEAP DEVICE BASED ON DIELECTRIC SPECTROSCOPY FOR FRESHNESS ASSESSMENT OF RAINBOW TROUT (*ONCORHYNCHUS MYKISS*)

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Abstract

In the present work we discussed about a non-destructive device set up for a rapid and reliable freshness assessment of rainbow trout during 10 days of storage in ice. The device was characterised by a Vector Network Analyser interfaced with an open coaxial probe to be placed in contact with fish eye. The acquisition of both spectral real and imaginary parts of the S11 scattering quality by Quality Index Method (QIM) were carried out. Partial Least Squares regression (PLS) predictive models of the demerit scores related to fish eye attributes (eye pupil and eye shape) and of the day of storage were set up. Main results showed that both real and imaginary part of the S11 decrease as a function of storage time. The combination with multivariate analysis allowed to set up predictive models of the storage time and the demerit scores with R^2 values up to 0.946 (RMSE = 0.88 days) and 0.942 (RMSE = 3.17 demerit scores related to the fish eyes attributes), respectively (external validation). Even though preliminary, the proposed cheap solution appears a useful tool for the freshness assessment of rainbow trout.

Keywords: dielectric properties, principal component analysis, sensory analysis, shelf life

Practical application

This work shows that dielectric properties have potential to discriminate stored fish according to their freshness quality. A device based on this principle can play a big role in the post-harvest processes, contributing to a higher product quality and safety and supporting producers and retailers during the qualitative inspections.

6.1 Introduction

Fish products provides consumer with a variety of high-value components, such as essential amino acids, n-3 fatty acids and important micronutrients. Therefore their consumption, production, and commercialisation are increasing worldwide (Hoffmire *et al.*, 2012; Calder, 2018; Mohanty *et al.*, 2019; Chen *et al.*, 2022). Aquaculture production of rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) in the EU reached about 210 thousand tonnes in 2019, being the most valuable freshwater species on the continent (FEAP, 2019). Rainbow trout can be found on European markets all year round, presented in several ways, whole or filleted, fresh or smoked. Whole fresh portion trout is by far the more commercialised, however, fresh fish are highly perishable products with quite a brief shelf-life. Spoilage activities occurring in fish during storage involves the changing of several chemical and

physical properties including moisture content, water activity and texture and follow enzymatic autolysis, oxidation, and microbial degradation mechanisms (Ghaly *et al.*, 2010). These activities start immediately after harvesting as a result of the presence of autolytic enzymes, high water activity, low pH and high content of unsaturated fatty acids, which create the optimal conditions for bacterial growth (Lougovois, 2005; Alasalvar, Grigor and Ali, 2010). The biochemical and physical changes that occur during product shelf-life are mainly related to enzymes that remain active after death and thus promote protein degradation and lipid oxidation (Huss H.H. 1995). These processes involve the formation of volatile organic compounds responsible for off-flavors and the deterioration of sensorial and nutritional quality (Whitfield, 1999). The above cited changes can be partially slowed down by the storage under controlled temperatures (e.g. melting ice) and the application of strict inspection controls (Badiani *et al.*, 2013). According to the EC regulation No 853/2004 (European Parliament, 2004), “Fresh fishery products mean unprocessed fishery products, whether whole or prepared, including products packaged under vacuum or in modified atmosphere, that have not undergone any treatment to ensure preservation other than chilling”. As a result, freshness is one of the major contributor to the quality of fish as well as the major attribute which influence the market value and the consumers’ willingness to buy fresh fish. In addition, freshness is associated with important food safety concerns as it is directly linked with several health risks for consumers (Olafsdóttir *et al.*, 1997; Rocculi *et al.*, 2019). Traditional freshness analytical methods are based on quantitative chemical, microbiological and physical techniques aimed at assessing different parameters generally recognised as indicators of fish post-mortem changes. Chemical indicators of fish spoilage are mainly represented by trimethylamine (TMA), total volatile basic nitrogen (TVB-N), free fatty acids (FFA), thiobarbituric acid value (TBA), K value generated from the autolytic decomposition of adenosine triphosphate (ATP) while total viable bacteria count (TVC) and colour and texture attributes are representative of microbial and physical properties measurements, respectively. Generally, these methods are time consuming, expensive, and destructive (Prabhakar *et al.*, 2020). Sensory evaluation is a commonly used method for the assessment of fish freshness. In European Union, its application in fish inspection services is defined in the EC Regulation No 2406/96 (European Parliament, 1996) (Luten and Martinsdottir, 1997; García *et al.*, 2017) with Traditional Freshness Quality Grading Systems. This method is easily applied by single assessors, but with the limitation of being subjective as only one assessor practices the assessment and categorization is sometimes forced (Botta J.R. 1995). In addition to the use of these tables, the quality index method (QIM) is a widely used approach (Freitas, Vaz-Pires and Câmara, 2021). This method is based on a scheme developed by the Tasmanian Food Research Unit (TFRU), Freshness Quality Grading System for Intact Fish (Bremner, 1985) and has to be

specifically designed for each fish species. A number of QIM schemes have been developed for the main commercial fish species including Atlantic salmon (Sveinsdottir *et al.*, 2003), cod (Cardenas Bonilla, Sveinsdottir and Martinsdottir, 2007) and sea bream (Sant'Ana, Soares and Vaz-Pires, 2011). This method is based on the selection of several spoilage-related attributes of a particular fish species such as eyes, skin, gills, smell, and texture. Each attribute has assigned a demerit score ranging normally from 0, for fresh product, to 2 or 3 for decayed product. The sum of all scores gives the Quality Index demerit score, the lower the score the fresher the fish. Developing a QIM for a particular fish species involves selecting the more appropriate and suitable attributes in order to observe a linear increase in Quality Index demerit score with time in ice storage. This method is inexpensive, non-destructive and rapid, but it requires a trained panel (Bernardi, Mársico and Freitas, 2013; Freitas, Vaz-Pires and Câmara, 2021). The need for a rapid, cheap, and non-destructive method for freshness evaluation of fish products is pushing research to find alternatives. The state of the art of indirect and non-invasive techniques applied to fish freshness assessment mainly covers e-sensing techniques, optical spectroscopic solutions, and nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) (Franceschelli *et al.*, 2021). These approaches are commonly combined with statistical algorithms able to extrapolate qualitative and quantitative models describing the variability occurring in the fish during storage. E-sensing techniques, including electronic noses (El Barbri *et al.*, 2008) and tongues (Ruiz-Rico *et al.*, 2013), colorimetric sensor array (Morsy *et al.*, 2016) and computer vision systems (Rocculi *et al.*, 2019), are deeply investigated because of their ability to simulate the human sensorial perceptiveness. In addition, the physicochemical and structural properties of the fish samples have been researched by modelling information coming from Fluorescence (Omwange *et al.*, 2020), Infrared (Tito, Rodemann and Powell, 2012), Hyperspectral Imaging (Cheng, Nicolai and Sun, 2016) and Raman spectroscopy (Herrero, 2008). These solutions have aroused great interest because of being rapid and contactless, even though considered expensive in that they require the use of trained operators. Indirect techniques cover also those based on fish dielectric properties explored by few works conducted by using time domain reflectometry technique (Kent *et al.*, 2004), impedance analysers (Wang *et al.*, 2008), commercial freshness meters (Vaz-Pires *et al.*, 2008) and open-ended coaxial probe (Iaccheri *et al.*, 2022). According to Iaccheri *et al.* (2022), dielectric constant and loss factor, acquired in the 250 to 2400 MHz spectral range, decrease as a function of fish eyes storage time. Therefore, dielectric spectroscopy (based on scattering parameter) appears to be a promising technique in the assessment of the eye dehydration during fish storage. This study represents a preliminary step in the exploration of rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) freshness through the application of a rapid and cheap spectroscopic technique based on the fish dielectric properties. Measurements of real and

imaginary part of the reflection (S11 scattering parameter) acquired on fish eye at different storage time were combined with those obtained through the application of a specific QIM scheme by a trained sensory panel. Main results can be useful for the setting up of a novel rapid and non-destructive method for fish freshness evaluation, which will support producers and retailers in the busy commercial setting.

6.2 Materials and Methods

6.2.1 Storage condition and experimental plan

Fresh-farmed rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) from a commercial producer were delivered to the Laboratory of Fish Quality Evaluation at the University of Bologna (Cesenatico, Italy) for three distinct storage trials between April and June 2021, following what is described in detail by Bakert K (2006) in "Seafood Research from Fish to Dish - Quality, Safety and Processing of Wild and Farmed Fish.". The fish had been slaughtered by ice-killing (hypothermia), packed with flaked ice into polystyrene boxes and delivered to the laboratory within 3 - 4 h from harvesting. Upon arrival, the fish were randomly divided into batches of 8 individuals, covered with ice and stored gutted in a refrigerator set at $0 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. On the day of analysis one batch was removed from the refrigerator. Each fish was coded, its mass (g) and its length (mm) were measured and then it was placed randomly on white trays on the evaluation desks. The first two storage trials were conducted as preliminary tests with the aim of setting up the Quality Index scheme. In detail, for each storage trial, a total of 80 trout were considered and 8 fish for each day of storage (0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 days) were assessed. For the third storage trial, a total of 48 trout were considered and 8 fish for each day of storage (0, 2, 4, 6, 8, and 10 days) were assessed. At each considered day of storage, sensory evaluation, Torrymeter assessment and spectral acquisitions were carried out. The length of storage was chosen on the basis of several research work, evidencing that, based on microbiological and sensorial data, the endpoint of whole rainbow trout edibility, whenever stored in ice, is between 9 and 12 days (Rezaei *et al.*, 2008; Tavakoli *et al.*, 2018). Moreover, as laid down by the trout producer, a maximum shelf-life of 7 days from harvesting has to be considered.

6.2.2 Sensory evaluation

Sensory evaluation was performed by a trained panel of four assessors (sex ratio 1:1, 25:45 age range) according to the Quality Index Method (QIM). This sensory approach is based on the

freshness assessment scheme proposed for rainbow trout by Grigorakis *et al.* 2018 and previously developed for Atlantic salmon by Sveinsdottir *et al.* 2003. Some modifications to the original scheme were implemented during the two preliminary storage trials, in order to best match the spoilage features occurring in the rainbow trout used in this experiment. In the way it is structured, and provided that fish is continuously kept under melting ice, QIM demerit score is linearly related to the storage time. Modifications were addressed to those attributes that least fit the linear model in terms of R². In detail, the attribute “texture”, composed of two description points in the original scheme, was increased to four. The attribute “abdomen odour” was removed as redundant, because the panellists were not able to discriminate any differences with the general “skin odour”. In addition, some minor adjustments were applied to the description of the attributes, to better match the external features of the rainbow trout used in this experiment. The so developed QIM scheme is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Quality index method scheme developed for rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*).

Quality parameter	Description	Demerit
<i>Skin</i>		
Colour / appearance	Pearl-shiny, green glass spots on the back	0
	Less shiny, slight metallic-pink discolouration on the side	1
	Greenish colour spread, pink-orange discoloration on the side and gill cover	2
	Green-grey discolouration and attenuation of the pink-orange nuance on the lateral side and gill cover	3
Mucus	Clear, shiny, and abundant	0
	Less clear, more viscous, and less abundant	1
	Milky, coagulated, and scarce	2
Odour	Fresh grass, river weed, cucumber	0
	Neutral to metallic smell	1
	Metallic, damp cellar and slight musty smell	2
	Oxidised blood smell, sour and decaying vegetation	3
Texture	Rigor	0
	Post rigor, firm, elastic	1
	Less firm, less elastic	2
	Soft	3
<i>Abdomen</i>		
Colour / appearance	Pure white / silver flecks, solid	0
	Whitish / greyish discoloration, slight longitudinal depression	1
	Yellowish / dark grey discoloration, evident longitudinal depression	2
<i>Eyes</i>		
Pupil	Limpid, black with metal shiny	0
	Lightly opaque, greyish discolouration	1
	Mat, grey	2
Shape	Convex shape	0
	Flat	1
	Slightly sunken	2
<i>Gills</i>		
Colour / appearance	Bright red, burgundy (Pantone 19-1617)	0
	Marsala red (Pantone 18-1438) and apical discoloration	1
	Totally discoloured, grey-yellowish colour	2
Mucus	Glossy, clear	0
	Filamentous, milky	1
	Yellow, clotted, and filamentous	2
Odour	Fresh grass, river weed	0
	Neutral to metallic smell	1
	Oxidised blood, fish bowels, mushroom smell	2
	Rotten, sulphurous, decaying vegetation	3
<i>Total demerit points</i>		0 – 24

Sensory evaluation was conducted in a lab which complies with the structural (dimensional and colour) requirements of the ISO standard defining general criteria for the design of sensory analysis rooms (ISO 8589:2014, Sensory analysis - General guidance for the design of test rooms), with minimal disturbance, at room temperature and under a white fluorescent light (Philips Master TL-D 36 W/65, average intensity of 1200 lux on the working area, colour temperature of 6500 K). Assessor, while working, had a distance of one meter from each other.

6.2.3 Torrymeter freshness assessment

Changes in chemical and physical properties occurring during storage as a consequence of spoilage were assessed by using a commercial Fish Freshness Meter “295 – Torrymeter” (Distell, Fauldhouse, West Lothian, UK), according to the procedure described by Lougovois et al. (Lougovois et al.,2003). By means of two pairs of concentrically arranged electrodes, the meter converts electronically measured phase angle between the current (A) and voltage (V) on a 0 - 18 scale that increases with fish freshness. Before sensory evaluation, two measurements were taken on the left and the right side were taken for each sample by applying the meter probe directly to the portion of meat just behind the gill cover, above the lateral line. Before each measurement, the electrodes were cleaned to remove debris (scales and mucus) that could compromise the measurement. The meter readings were read on the digital display.

6.2.4 Spectral acquisition

Spectral acquisitions were conducted immediately after the sensory evaluation procedure by placing a coaxial probe in contact with the fish eyes. For each fish, both right and left eyes were acquired. The layout of the instrumental chain is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Setup of the instrumental chain with typical signal output and a picture of the contact between fish eye and the coaxial probe.

The Vector Network Analyser (VNA Nano V2, HXCQS in collaboration with OwOComm, China) is interfaced with an open coaxial probe connected to the instrument via port S11 through a semi-rigid coaxial cable for high frequencies (50 Ohm). Cable instrument and probe were assembled using specially made supports. The open coaxial probe was obtained starting from a female SMA connector, for the electronic boards, by turning and subsequent surface gilding of the brass. The VNA selected for the present research is quite a cheap portable instrument available on the market (about 100 €). Nano VNA V2 is a two-port vector network analyser, CH0 and CH1 (reflection/transmission), designed for frequencies from 50 kHz to 3 GHz. In the present research only the CH0 port was used and the scattering parameters S11 (reflection), real and imaginary part, was measured. The calibration of the assembled instrumental chain was performed to remove the three typical systematic errors in one port measurements: directivity, source match and reflection tracking (Chen, Arnold and Small, 2004). For the purpose, its own commercial calibration kit (SMA-type 50 Ohm, HXCQS in collaboration with OwOComm, China) was used, accounting for open, short and load calibration acquisitions and corrections. The spectra were acquired with the Nano-VNA-saver software (GNU, General Public License, version 0.3.8, Rune Broberg) for the whole frequency range 50kHz-3GHz, averaging three consecutive acquisitions of 301 spectral points.

6.2.5 Data analysis

Significant differences in mass (g), length (mm), QIM and Torrymeter scores acquired during the third storage trial, were explored between means during the storage by using a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and Tukey's Post hoc test ($P < 0.05$). The assumptions related to data normal

distribution and homogeneity of variances were explored through Anderson Darling's test and Levene's test, respectively. The coefficient of determination R^2 obtained from a linear regression between QIM attributes, QIM scores and days of storage were explored and discussed. In addition, QIM scheme attributes were analysed by principal component analysis (PCA) to better evidence the role of each sensorial attribute in the discrimination of the samples according to the storage time and their relationships (Minitab 19.0.1, Pennsylvania State University, USA). For both real and imaginary parts of S11, average values of measurement conducted on right and left eyes were used as independent variables for Partial Least Squares regression analysis (PLS) with the aim of setting up predictive models of the demerit scores related to the fish eyes attributes (as a sum of the total demerit points) and of the day of storage. Data were arranged in a 48 (samples) \times 301 (spectral variables) matrix. Loading weights were exploited to select the spectral range, considering that higher values related to the frequency portion gives a huge contribution to explain the variability. In this way, the lower frequencies were not considered for the analysis, and the selected frequency range was 1.2-3 GHz. The calibration sample set was used for computing the calibration models. Validation was then performed to well understand how the developed model would perform with unknown samples. Test set validation was applied. Seven samples which were not included in the training stage were randomly selected and used to validate the models. The procedure was repeated ten times and results in terms of coefficient of determination (R^2), Root Mean Square Error (RMSEC and RMSECV) and significative PLS components (PCs) both for calibration and validation were reported and discussed (Unscrambler software, version 9.7, CAMO, Oslo, Norway).

6.3 Results and Discussion

6.3.1 External appearance

Examples of pictures of rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) captured during the storage trial are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Examples of rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) appearance during 10 days of ice storage.

Ice chilling is the most popular storage method used in fishery and aquaculture industry to delay the onset of spoilage, which is related to oxidative, enzymatic and microbial degradation (Badiani *et al.*, 2013; Kontominas *et al.*, 2021). As expected, during the analysed 10 days of ice storage, changes in the eye, skin and gill appearance were observed. The discoloration of the rainbow trout skin occurred over the storage time can be explained by the oxidation of the carotenoid pigments. Astaxanthin, an abundant carotenoid pigment in fish, is converted into colourless carbonyl compounds by a lipoxygenase enzyme present in the skin tissue and atmospheric oxygen. Colour fading is amplified by the coagulation of mucus, due to the dehydration of the mucin glycoprotein, which modify the reflection of the light on the fish skin (Lougovois, 2005). More generally, oxidative process occurring in fish during spoilage, involves the reaction of unsaturated fatty acids with atmospheric oxygen to form hydroperoxides. These are decomposed to carbonyl compounds (e.g. aldehydes and ketones), which are responsible also of the off-flavours appearance (Kontominas *et al.*, 2021; Nie *et al.*, 2022). Off-flavours are intensified by the autolytic degradation of nucleotides, the bacterial reduction of trimethylamine oxide (TMAO) to trimethylamine (TMA) (Barrett and Kwan, 1985) and other microbial spoilage process (e.g. ammonia and hydrogen sulphide producing bacteria) (Gram, 1992; Lougovois, Kyranas and Kyranas, 2003). The odour of rainbow trout assessed during the storage trial was of fresh vegetables notes (e.g. cucumber and river weeds) until 4 days of storage. Following 2 days where the odour appeared as neutral or slightly metallic, until reaching the characteristic off-flavours (e.g. oxidised blood, decaying vegetation) after 6 days of storage. The colour of the gills assessed in rainbow trout appeared bright red or burgundy (Pantone 19-1617) with a glossy and clear mucus until 2 days of storage. As the time increased, gill colour passed from marsala red (Pantone 18-1438) with apical discolouration and a filamentous and milky mucus on day 4. After 8 days of storage, mainly because of microbial growth and blood oxidation, gills acquired a grey-yellowish colour with yellow coagulated mucus. The eyes pupil tended to be grey and opaque over the period of storage. This could be attributed to the internal chemical changes which lead to external changes such as colour and appearance in fish post mortem (Dowlati *et al.*, 2013). Moreover, with increasing storage time, the shape of the eye gradually passed from being flat to concave (sunken), as it is reported in literature (Lougovois, 2005). With regard to the texture, rainbow trout presented a firm and hard consistency, often in rigor mortis, until 2 days of storage. A progressive post-mortem softening of the fish muscle was observed during the storage, as a result of enzymatic degradation generated by the activity of endogenous proteases on myofibrillar proteins (Cheng *et al.*, 2014).

6.3.2 Sensorial evaluation and Torrymeter freshness assessment

Mean values of the mass (g), length (mm), QIM and Torrymeter scores acquired during the third storage trial are summarised in Table 2. The table also shows the results of the Analysis of Variance conducted within the same analysed parameter according to the storage time.

Table 2. Mass, length, QIM and Torrymeter scores of rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) during 10 days of storage in ice

Storage (days)	Mass (g)	Length (mm)	QIM	Torrymeter
0	307.4 (23.6)	299 (6)	0.4 ^a (0.5)	13.1 ^a (0.8)
2	332.4 (62.5)	314 (17)	5.0 ^b (1.5)	13.1 ^a (0.7)
4	356.3 (43.5)	312 (6)	11.4 ^c (2.3)	12.6 ^{ab} (0.8)
6	361.6 (61.2)	312 (16)	13.9 ^c (2.4)	11.6 ^{bc} (1.3)
8	338.3 (51.8)	307 (14)	19.5 ^d (1.6)	10.5 ^c (1.1)
10	328.0 (313)	300 (5)	22.5 ^e (1.0)	11.0 ^c (1.0)

Data are given as the mean (n = 8) ± SD (in brackets). Different superscript letters, within column, indicate significant differences among samples during storage ($P \leq .05$).

As expected, storage time significantly influences both QIM and Torrymeter scores. After post hoc test, non-significant differences in QIM mean values emerged between samples stored for 4 and 6 days. The QIM scheme developed in this work, shown in Table 1, reached its highest score after 10 days of storage and consisted of 10 attributes for a total of 24 demerit scores. Other QIM schemes developed for rainbow trout focused on the degradation of the sensorial characteristic on longer storage periods such as 17 days (Grigorakis *et al.*, 2018) and 12 days (Diler and Genç, 2018). However, the shelf-life of rainbow trout is considered to be somewhat shorter (Rezaei *et al.*, 2008; Tavakoli *et al.*, 2018). This is confirmed in this experiment by the onset of an unpleasant smell, which appeared after 6 days of storage, and become unacceptable on the day 10. Significant differences were observed in Torrymeter mean values between samples at 0, 2, 4 and samples at 8 and 10 days of storage. Differently from QIM, Torrymeter assessment appears to discriminate trout samples only into two clusters of freshness; respect to day 0, the first significant differences between means appeared only starting from 6 days of storage. Torrymeter is a useful tool to evaluate fish freshness over several days, although less discriminative on shorter storage time (Cheyne, 1975). According to the manufacturer's manual, with regard to salmon (*Atlantic salmon*) stored in ice, a Torrymeter score above 12 corresponds to a fish harvested for less than 3 days and to "Extra" on the EC freshness grade. A Torrymeter score between 9 and 10 corresponds to a 5 - 8 days fish and to an "A" on the EC freshness grade. Results of the coefficient of determination R^2

obtained from linear regression models between each QIM quality parameters, QIM total and days of storage are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Coefficient of determination (R^2) for each quality parameter assessed during 10 days of ice storage with the QIM scheme developed for rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*).

Quality attribute	R^2 (all samples)	R^2 (mean values)
Skin colour / appearance	0.788	0.942
Skin mucus	0.821	0.942
Skin odour	0.809	0.936
Texture	0.819	0.936
Abdomen colour / appearance	0.751	0.961
Eyes pupil	0.816	0.941
Eyes shape	0.819	0.979
Gills colour / appearance	0.506	0.982
Gills mucus	0.592	0.876
Gills odour	0.848	0.979
QIM total	0.948	0.988

The results refer to both models calculated starting from all the considered samples or the mean values. By considering linear models obtained by using all samples, the gill colour / appearance and gill mucus attributes were characterised by the lowest R^2 values. As evidenced in Table 3 and Figure 3, a coefficient of determination R^2 of 0.948 was observed for QIM total demerit point. Passing to the models obtained from mean values, the R^2 values increased as expected.

Figure 3. Linear regression between quality index demerit score and storage time assessed during the third storage trial with the QIM scheme developed for rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*).

6.3.3 Principal component analysis

The scores plot obtained from Principal Component Analysis (PCA) conducted by using the QIM quality parameters measured during the third storage trial and the storage time is shown Figure 4.

Figure 4. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) scores plot including all quality parameters evaluated in the QIM scheme developed for rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) and storage time.

The first component (PC1) accounted for the 79.96 % of the variability and appeared to model differences related to the storage time while the second component (PC2), accounting for the 5.31 %, seems to explain the variability between samples within the same storage time. As indicated in Figures 5 and 6, showing the loadings values associated to PC1 and PC2, respectively, PC1, associated with storage time, appears less influenced by the gill colour/appearance and gill mucus quality attributes compared to the other analysed attributes. On the contrary, gill colour/appearance is the quality attribute that more affect PC2 and therefore the variability between samples at the same day of storage.

Figure 5. PC1 (left) and PC2 (right) loadings plots.

Figure 6. Real and imaginary part of S11 as a function of different storage time. The legend reports the sum of QIM total demerit point related to trout eyes.

6.3.4 Spectral assessments

Real and imaginary part of the scattering parameter S11 (reflection) are shown in Figure 6 for trout eyes samples during storage time. Averaged spectra of trout eyes were shown as a function of the sum of QIM total demerit point related to trout eyes, such as shape and pupils' attributes. Figure 6 showed spectra variability also as a function of storage time. Particularly, the low portion of frequency range seems to give the lower contribute for variability description, both for real and imaginary part of reflection. Physical-chemical modification induced by post-mortem mechanisms influence the spectral response, as also previously reported for anchovy eyes (Iaccheri *et al.*, 2022).

The authors report a decrease in dielectric constant and loss factor due to freshness loss, explained by dehydration of eyes during storage time. According to Iaccheri *et al.*, (2022) real and imaginary part of permittivity decrease as a function of storage time and this could confirm the same behavior. Real and imaginary part of S11 spectra were used for PLS regression for QIM total demerit point of eyes and storage time estimation. Results in terms of R^2 , RMSE and PCs for both calibration and test set validation models are reported in Table 4, and 5.

Table 4. PLS results both for real and imaginary part for QIM estimation.

Total QIM estimation	R^2 calibration	RMSE calibration	R^2 validation	RMSE validation	PCs	
Real part of S11	1	0.993	1.09	0.912	3.64	6
	2	0.997	1.41	0.914	4.43	6
	3	0.997	0.72	0.956	2.83	6
	4	0.994	0.97	0.945	3.32	6
	5	0.993	1.09	0.910	3.77	6
	6	0.991	1.15	0.981	2.11	6
	7	0.992	1.11	0.977	1.94	6
	8	0.989	1.36	0.950	2.92	6
	9	0.996	0.84	0.928	3.40	6
	10	0.997	0.71	0.943	3.36	6
Imaginary part of S11	1	0.998	0.54	0.911	3.18	9
	2	0.996	0.82	0.936	3.04	8
	3	0.996	0.78	0.960	3.01	8
	4	0.996	0.85	0.949	2.26	8
	5	0.993	1.05	0.939	3.17	7
	6	0.987	1.45	0.969	2.18	6
	7	0.997	0.57	0.900	4.57	9
	8	0.985	1.52	0.962	2.72	6
	9	0.997	0.71	0.931	3.20	8
	10	0.990	1.25	0.946	3.02	7

Table 5. PLS results both for real and imaginary part for storage time estimation.

Storage time estimation	R ² calibration	RMSE calibration	R ² validation	RMSE validation	PCs	
Real part of S11	1	0.996	0.23	0.961	0.81	7
	2	0.98	0.47	0.947	1.1	7
	3	0.928	0.96	0.938	0.98	5
	4	0.994	0.28	0.945	0.79	6
	5	0.996	0.22	0.960	0.82	7
	6	0.993	0.3	0.912	1.05	6
	7	0.936	0.93	0.945	0.78	6
	8	0.982	0.47	0.957	0.85	5
	9	0.991	0.34	0.934	0.90	6
	10	0.995	0.24	0.956	0.73	7
Immaginary part of S11	1	0.991	0.32	0.967	0.76	7
	2	0.999	0.11	0.918	1.00	10
	3	0.994	0.27	0.970	0.61	7
	4	0.997	0.21	0.953	0.73	8
	5	0.993	0.28	0.947	0.85	7
	6	0.995	0.25	0.917	0.87	7
	7	0.989	0.37	0.920	0.96	6
	8	0.986	0.43	0.983	0.37	6
	9	0.982	0.47	0.964	0.73	6
	10	0.991	0.32	0.906	1.03	7

PLS regression model validated gave very good results in terms of coefficient of determination and related errors. Particularly, PLS models demonstrated very good prediction ability in terms of R² 0.946, 0.945 and RMSE 0.88 and 0.79 (mean value for real and imaginary part), and R² 0.942, 0.940, and RMSE 3.17, 3.03 (mean value for real and imaginary part), for storage time and QIM total demerit point of eyes respectively. As an example, predicted versus observed values of one PLS validated model for both estimation of QIM total demerit point of eyes and storage time were shown in Figures 7 and 8. Predicted versus observed values confirm the ability of the proposed instrumental chain based on a coaxial probe to estimates both storage time and QIM total demerit point of eyes. The instrumental method is affordable, rapid, simple, and non-destructive avoiding the possible personal impact that sensory evaluation could be subjected.

Figure 7. Predicted versus observed values for QIM estimation by using as predictors the real (R) and imaginary (I) part.

Figure 8. Predicted versus observed values for storage time by using as predictors the real (R) and imaginary (I) part.

6.4 Conclusion

A cheap and non-destructive device combined with multivariate statistical tools was set up aiming at exploring its ability in predicting the freshness of rainbow trout during a storage of 10 days in ice. The proposed solution was based on PLS regression models obtained by considering both real and imaginary part spectra of scattering parameter S11 acquired in the 50 kHz – 3 GHz frequency range as independent variables. The acquisitions were conducted by placing a coaxial probe connected with VNA in contact with the fish eye. The day of storage and the demerit point calculated from a

specific Quality Index Method scheme were chosen as dependent variables. According to the results, apart from gill colour/appearance and gill mucus, all the considered sensorial attributes well describe the degradative changes occurring in the fish during the storage in ice. Both real and imaginary part spectra also contain information related to these changes. The tested device appears to be able to predict the storage time with R^2 value up to 0.946 and RMSE of 0.88 days and the total demerit scores associated to fish-eye with R^2 value of 0.946 and RMSE of 3.17. This simple solution can play a big role in the post-harvest processes, contributing to a higher product quality and safety and supporting producers and retailers during the qualitative inspections.

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7. DISCUSSIONS

Sensory analysis is not new in the food industry, but its application as a fundamental tool for new product development and quality control has not always received due recognition and acclaim. This seems to be largely due to a lack of awareness of what it can bring to product research, development, and marketing and a concern that this "too academic" principle is impractical (Pagliarini, 2021).

The sensory analysis is also used to highlight the strengths and characteristics of a product, such as in the case of research and development products in which alternative ingredients, food scraps or by-products, are used. It can also be used to evaluate the same characteristics over time, to highlight alterations in one of the sensory components at a particular time or over time.

The results of this PhD project involved the application of sensory methods, and in one case also consumer science, in which several aquaculture products were studied.

Specifically, the products covered by this Phd project were analyzed, depending on the objective pursued, by consumers and specially trained judges during the first year of the PhD project, since, at the Department of Veterinary Medical Sciences there was no trained panel.

The creation of this sensory group made it possible, in the first study, to compare the effects of different levels of dietary inclusion (5, 10 and 15%) of *Hermetia illucens* larvae meal on the sensory, technological and nutritional quality of gilthead sea bream (*Sparus aurata*) fillets were compared. The fish were fed the experimental diets for 113 days. The Quantitative Descriptive Analysis (QDA[®]) method is based on the idea that the sensory impact of a product is produced by all identifiable sensory attributes. These are called "descriptors". Therefore, the descriptive method is used to describe a particular product.

Mean values represent the intensities of descriptors placed on unstructured scales and arranged in a spider's web graph.

The results showed that the addition of defatted meal from *Hermetia illucens* larvae did not cause an unpleasant taste to the sea bream fillets. No significant differences were found in the appearance, mouthfeel and texture, while differences appeared in the odour and taste characteristics of the "boiled chicken breast". Furthermore, the quality characteristics of the fillets showed no significant differences between the treatments.

The absence of significant differences ($P > 0.05$) in most of the attributes examined provides consumers with further evidence that feeding sea bream with diets containing *Hermetia illucens* meal has no negative impact on the taste and quality of the fillets.

We can conclude that through the use of the QDA[®] method and thus sensory analysis, it was possible to describe the characteristics, all positive by the way, of sea bream fillets that support the thesis of

the use of sustainable, circular and environmentally friendly proteins with a low environmental impact.

In the second study, the effects of different levels of inclusion in the diet (30, 60 and 100 %) of *Tenebrio molitor* larvae meal on the sensory quality of trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) fillets were evaluated, again using the Quantitative Descriptive Analysis (QDA[®]) method and thus sensory analysis, which showed no significant differences between the sensory profiles of products fed with the different scientific treatments and therefore no sensory alterations in trout fillets. Furthermore, the acceptability of this protein source to consumers through consumer science was evaluated in this study, showing that there is still a neophobia towards this alternative protein.

The work described in this scientific manuscript is relevant because it adds knowledge on the study of the acceptability of this protein source to consumers. This work is also interesting with regard to one of the most popular topics at the moment, namely, the circular economy. In fact, the aquaculture product fed with insect meal is a possible future reality that could obviate the problem of fish shortage and thus present itself as a viable option for replacing the fish meal within the feed available for aquaculture.

The limitation of this study is the national/cultural context because it was only proposed with Spanish consumers, which means that future experiments should include a cross-cultural comparison. Another important factor to consider is taste education, an important tool to change negative attitudes and expectations towards edible insects (Sogari et al. 2018).

In addition, it seems that indirect approval from others (family and friends) can be a valuable avenue for the introduction and spread of entomophagy (Sogari 2015; Sogari, Menozzi and Mora 2017).

In the third study, an inexpensive, non-destructive device combined with multivariate statistical tools was created with the aim of exploring its ability to predict the freshness of rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) during a 10-day storage period on ice.

Acquisitions were conducted by placing a coaxial probe connected to the VNA (Vector Network Analyser) in contact with the fisheye. The day of storage and the demerit point calculated according to a specific Quality Index Method (QIM) scheme were chosen as dependent variables.

The QIM method is an effective sensory method for assessing changes occurring in the fish product and is therefore a reliable and standardised measure of product freshness.

According to the results, apart from gill colour/appearance and gill mucus, all sensory attributes considered describe well the degradative changes occurring in fish during storage in ice. The spectra of the real and imaginary part also contain information about these changes. The tested device seems to be able to predict the storage time with an R² value of 0.946 and the total demerit score associated with the fisheye with an R² value of 0.946. Although preliminary, this simple and inexpensive

solution can play an important role in post-harvest processes, contributing to higher product quality and safety and supporting producers and retailers during quality inspections.

Because fish products are so perishable, assessing their freshness is particularly important, both for commercial and hygienic purposes. In addition, increasing supply and demand from all regions of the world require increasingly precise freshness assessment techniques.

Formal control is still based on sensory evaluation, a method that has no objective criteria and is universally valid because it is left to the experience and discretion of the operator (Cianti et al., 2007).

QIM is today considered the most effective sensory method for assessing the freshness of fish products. Its advantages are expressed in practicality, ease and speed of implementation, non-destruction and the ability to estimate the shelf life of the product. This can be extremely useful for operators in the sector: for example, a trader may want to know how long a purchased product will be saleable if properly stored in ice.

According to some authors, with the QIM method it is possible to estimate shelf life with an error of 1-2 days, which is also acceptable, compared to classical laboratory methods that require chemical and microbiological experiments to be performed. difficult to implement on a regular basis (Lougovois et al., 2003).

The weakness (as well as, the strength) of the method lies in its species specificity. Existing evaluation scheme only cover a limited number of fish species. Therefore, it would be desirable for research to further contribute to the validation of assessment schemes applicable to fish species for which there is still no species-specific scheme.

This thesis highlights how sensory analysis is an important tool for the enhancement and communication of product quality characteristics and how relevant the development of quality indicators using modern research methods is. New knowledge methods could be used to promote these products to Italian and/or European consumers, as well as to better understand the freshness and characters of aquaculture products.

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